

MOTIVATIONAL ORIENTATION ON LEARNING ENGLISH AMONG BEED STUDENT: A CONVERGENT PARALLEL STUDY

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Motivational Orientation on Learning English among Beed Student: A Convergent Parallel Study

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Abstract

This study aimed to describe the lived experiences of BEED students in a local college on their motivational orientation on learning English. This study engaged mixed method design, utilizing convergent parallel approach. The participants of the study were the second year students enrolled in BEED program. There were 83 students who were randomly selected for the quantitative and 14 for the qualitative: 7 for in-depth interview and 7 for focus group discussion which were purposively selected. The researcher conducted thematic analysis to examine the qualitative data. This involved recording participants' responses, organizing them, and reducing them into themes through coding and refining the codes during qualitative data analysis. In the quantitative phase, specific statistical tools were applied, including the mean to determine the average participant responses and the standard deviation to measure the variation in survey answers. Based on the result of the study, it was determined that the level of motivational orientation on learning English among BEED students is very high. Additionally, the qualitative phase of the study uncovered the lived experiences, coping strategies, and insights of elementary education regarding their motivational orientation towards learning English. Based on participants' responses, 11 essential themes emerged. The results from the qualitative and quantitative converged when they are being corroborated.

Keywords: *motivational orientation, mixed method, convergent-parallel, elementary education students*

Introduction

Students frequently encounter difficulties in their journey of learning English. What often occurs in the classroom is that students lack enthusiasm and motivation to learn English, as they are primarily focused on simply passing the course. They tend to not pay attention to the teacher and fail to absorb the material due to their lack of interest. Even when they do learn something, they tend to forget it quickly. The ineffective implementation of teaching methods often leaves learners feeling uncurious or disengaged during the learning process, which negatively impacts their motivation, as they lose interest in learning English (Syuhada & Fatimah, 2021).

In the context of the global stage, with a specific focus on Vietnam, the VNU University of Engineering and Technology has been diligently working to create additional opportunities for students to enhance their English language proficiency. However, the advancement in English language skills among the student body remains less than desirable. This suboptimal progress can be attributed to the display of negative behaviors by the students, which in turn indicates a lack of motivation to learn English as a foreign language. Despite the university's efforts, the overall enthusiasm and commitment to English language acquisition appear to be low. This challenge underscores the importance of further exploration and intervention to address the root causes of this motivation deficit, ensuring a more effective approach to English language education. Achieving this goal is crucial for preparing students to participate in the global arena, where English proficiency is often a vital skill for success (Nguyen, 2019).

In the Philippines, particularly at UM Panabo Campus, it has been observed that students demonstrate significant inadequacies in delivering reports, conducting oral presentations, and writing effective essays in the classroom, as well as in meeting teachers' course requirements. Issues such as improper use of both oral and written language, passive and unassertive behavior in English discourse, and deficiencies in basic English communication skills are evident. These problems stem from students' lack of motivation to learn English. Several factors contribute to this challenge, creating a difficult environment for English language education. These factors include a widespread lack of self-confidence, fear of making mistakes, educators who may also lack motivation, and limited access to essential learning resources. Together, these issues have caused a significant decline in students' motivation to learn English (Mosqueda, 2022).

This study holds social significance as proficiency in English is crucial for the success of BEED students. As prospective educators, mastering English is vital, given its role as the primary medium of instruction in numerous educational environments, facilitating clear communication with students. Consequently, it is imperative for future educators to be driven and committed to enhancing their English proficiency. Additionally, this research warrants attention due to the potential repercussions of a lack of motivation in learning English, which could lead to issues and complexities in the quality of English learning experiences for BEED students. Addressing this problem promptly is essential for ensuring a robust educational foundation.

In my literature review, I have found related studies such as the study of Setiyadi et al. (2019) entitled "Exploring Motivational Orientations of English as Foreign Language (EFL) learners" and the study of Yuwita (2023) entitled, "Investigating University Students' Motivational Orientation towards English Language Learning". None of this were similar to this study as this focuses more on the motivational orientation of BEED students from KCAST. Also, this study will utilize mixed method approach that combines a quantitative and qualitative method to measure the level of motivational orientation of BEED students in KCAST which is less explored in the body of knowledge. These premises prompted the researcher to propose this study. Copies of the study will be disseminated to

the various research conferences and concerned agencies to facilitate scholarly exchange and utilization of research-based discovery.

Research Questions

In this study, convergent parallel mixed methods research was used in broadly examining the level of motivational orientation on learning English among BEED students in KCAST. Specifically, this sought to answer the following research questions.

1. What is the level of motivational orientation on learning English among BEED students in KCAST?
2. What are the lived experiences, coping mechanism, and insights of BEED students in dealing with their motivational orientation in learning English?
3. To what extent do qualitative results corroborate with quantitative results?

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, the researcher employed the convergent parallel mixed methods. It is a non-experimental design combining the elements of quantitative and qualitative approaches. It is convergent parallel since the study will use quantitative data collection and analysis and qualitative data collection and analysis occurred at the same time and are then compared after the completion of the study (Tomasi et al., 2018). The method was used to examine and determine the level motivational orientation on learning English among BEED students. Further, it is often used to overcome a weakness in one method with the strength of another.

In the context of the study, this design utilized a mixed-method approach that combines quantitative and qualitative research methods to measure the level motivational orientation on learning English among BEED students. This enables researcher to acquire a more thorough and nuanced understanding of BEED students' motivational orientation in learning English. Quantitative data may uncover statistical trends and patterns, whereas qualitative data can reveal insights into the root causes and experiences of students.

Specifically, the quantitative component involved descriptive approach. Descriptive approach is a study designed to depict the participants in an accurate way. More simply putting descriptive approach is all about describing people who take part on the study. It is used to describe characteristics of a population phenomenon being studied. These kinds of categorical scheme are also known as descriptive categories.

Additionally, the BEED students of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology were asked to participate in a survey that has been specially designed for them. The research study received responses from 100 individuals. Participants' collective responses were used to produce a number of problems. In order to do this, proper statistical methods, including frequency, weighted mean, and standard deviation was used. Following these procedures, data were displayed and examined using descriptive statistics.

Conversely, in the qualitative phase of this study, the researcher adopted a phenomenological approach that reflects an epistemological perspective, acknowledging that truth can be seen in multiple, subjective ways. To gather qualitative data, focus group discussions and individual in-depth interviews were utilized, which proved effective in helping the researcher understand the community's social norms. These methods allowed for comprehensive data collection, enabling the researcher to achieve data saturation and to develop themes from the insights gathered during the interviews (Tripoli, 2014).

Thus, data was collected through focus group discussion and one-on-one in-depth interview of the participants. The interview guide consisted of questions for the seven chosen participants in one-on-one in-depth interview and seven participants for the focus group discussion. The questions were designed to elicit responses from the participants. Schedule of the interview was set in order to facilitate the proceedings and to consider the availability of the participants. Every detail of the responses was taken into consideration but those not relevant to the study will not be reflected.

Participants

The participants were selected based on their ability to provide valuable insights, address the research questions, and enhance the understanding of the phenomenon being examined (Kuper, Lingard & Levinson, 2008). Specifically, the key participants in this research were the second-year BEED students of Kapalong College of Agriculture Science and Technology.

Quantitative Phase

The participants in this research comprised second-year BEEEd-Generalist students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology during the initial semester of the academic year 2023-2024. The selection of these students as respondents was deliberate, aligning with the study's focus on motivational orientation in English learning among BEEEd students in the institution. Given the study's emphasis on second-year students within the BEEEd-Generalist program at the institution, it was deemed appropriate and valid to include second-year students specifically from Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology.

These individuals provided invaluable firsthand insights by responding to a comprehensive set of survey questions specifically designed to assess their motivational orientation in the context of English learning. The questionnaire was thoughtfully constructed to capture nuanced aspects of their motivational attitudes and beliefs in relation to the English learning process. Their responses played a pivotal

role in elucidating the motivational dynamics inherent in their pursuit of English language proficiency.

The research was carried out among second-year students enrolled in the BEED-Generalist program. The institution comprises a total of 104 second-year student consisting of 7 males and 48 females in BEED 2A, and 4 males and 45 females in BEED 2B. However, the study's sample size was determined by the statistician, encompassing 6 out of 7 males and 38 out of 48 females from BEED 2A. Similarly, the sample for BEED 2B included 3 out of 4 males and 36 out of 45 females. In aggregate, the study sampled 83 students from the total pool of 104 students in the BEED- Generalist program.

Table 1.1. Distribution of Respondents

<i>BEED</i>		<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
BEED 2A	Boys	7	6	5.37%
	Girls	48	38	36.83%
BEED 2B	Boys	4	3	3.07%
	Girls	45	36	34.53%
Total		104	83	79.81%

Qualitative Phase

In contrast, qualitative research employed purposeful subject selection using non-probability sampling, specifically the purposive sampling technique. The participants chosen was those who could provide the most insightful information for the research questions, enhancing the understanding of the studied phenomenon (Kuper et al., 2008). The qualitative phase involved 14 participants from the BEED-Generalist program at KCAST. Seven (7) for in-depth interviews and another seven (7) for focus group discussions. All participants must be 2nd-year BEED-Generalist students, and it is crucial to note that those involved in the qualitative phase should not have taken part in the data collection of the quantitative phase.

Table 1.2. Profiles of the Participants

<i>Assigned Code</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Year-Level</i>
IDI-01	Female	2nd year
IDI-02	Female	2nd year
IDI-03	Female	2nd year
IDI-04	Male	2nd year
IDI-05	Female	2nd year
IDI-06	Male	2nd year
IDI-07	Female	2nd year
FGD-01	Female	2nd year
FGD-02	Female	2nd year
FGD-03	Female	2nd year
FGD-04	Female	2nd year
FGD-05	Female	2nd year
FGD-06	Male	2nd year
FGD-07	Male	2nd year

Instrument

Research instruments are tools utilized for data collection, encompassing items like questionnaires, tests, structured interviews, and checklists. In this parallel mixed method study, two specific instruments, namely a survey questionnaire and an interview guide, were employed to efficiently obtain essential data from the participants (Seaman, 1991).

Quantitative Phase

The quantitative data needed for the investigation were provided by the instrument used during the quantitative phase of the study. During the quantitative phase, a survey questionnaire was adopted from the study of Abrar-Ur-Hassan (2014) to collect quantitative data from the participants. The first tool is a survey that will be used to collect information on the extent of motivational orientation on learning English. It included three parts: extrinsic orientation, international orientation, and intrinsic orientation. Participants respond on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 representing infrequently and 5 representing always. Refer to the variety of means, descriptions, and interpretations to determine their level of knowledge motivational orientation on learning English. The constructed survey questionnaire had prior reliability values that range from .53 to .77 which indicated that the instruments are reliable to measure the variables.

Qualitative Phase

The panel of experts scrutinized the use of the qualitative research guide questionnaire to ensure its validity in terms of its clarity, suitability, understandability, and capacity to elicit personal narratives, comments, opinions, and insights from the research participants. Additionally, the prepared open-ended questions were limited to three research issues and a maximum of five probing questions for

each. Additionally, it offered crucial closing elements that ensured the participants' opportunity to make further comments. In order to make sure that the transcription of the data is accurate, the researcher also provided copies of the transcriptions to the concerned participants. The objective also included reaching an agreement by comprehending various perspectives on the material.

Procedure

The procedure for gathering the data includes a number of steps. Quantitative and qualitative data was gathered concurrently, nearly at the same time. Parallel mixed-method data collection techniques were used to compare data from diverse sources, modify the data for comparison, or answer various types of inquiries (Creswell & Clark, 2007).

Quantitative Phase

The researcher first request permission from the Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology's office of the president to carry out this study in order to facilitate the collection of the required quantitative data. Additionally, the motivational orientation survey questionnaire, which was developed, was used in this study to gather quantitative data. In order to prevent participant mood changes during the quantitative data collection, the survey questionnaire was given to participants on the same day. The results were tallied, computed, and analyzed to corroborate with the results of the qualitative data.

Qualitative Phase

Focus group discussions and one-on-one in-depth interviews with participants was part of the qualitative data collection to obtain information about the participants' motivational orientation on learning English. The researcher asked the informants about their time availability for the in-person interviews before starting the focus group discussions and one-on-one in-depth interviews. The researcher also inquired about the location of the interviews. The researcher used a planned set of enabling questions during the one-on-one in-depth interview and also provided follow-up questions to ensure that all of the subjects' answers was covered. The researcher went into great detail during the interview about the individuals' ethical concerns.

Data Analysis

The tabulation of data and data analysis were completed immediately after all applicable data were obtained. The researcher employed thematic analysis to analyze the qualitative data, while specific statistical tools were utilized to analyze the data during the quantitative phase, ensuring a comprehensive examination of both qualitative and quantitative aspects of the study.

Quantitative Phase

In the analysis of quantitative data, descriptive statistics, such as the mean, were used to evaluate the average replies of the participants, and the standard deviation was used to assess the variability of the respondents' responses on the survey's motivational orientation questionnaire.

Qualitative Phase

However, participants' responses were recorded, arranged, and reduced to themes through a process of coding and condensing the codes in qualitative data analysis. A narrative, a table, or a set of figures were used to present the data. The researcher totally immersed themselves in the rich, descriptive data during the analysis of the qualitative data, employing coding and categorization techniques to arrange the data. The objective was to create themes that could be utilized to describe the BEED students' motivational orientation in learning English. Thus, qualitative analysis was an iterative process that involved generating and refining themes repeatedly as well as reading and rereading the data in order to get a final analysis of the data to shed light on the research objectives and provide insights into the participants' experiences in this context.

Ethical Considerations

In order to uphold the trust of the BEED-Generalist students from KCAST, the study prioritized their safety, anonymity, complete protection, and confidentiality as key concerns. Measures were taken to ensure that these ethical considerations were carefully addressed, aiming to maintain the trust of the participants throughout the course of the study.

The researcher diligently adhered to ethical principles including respect for persons, beneficence, justice, obtaining informed consent, and maintaining confidentiality to ensure that ethical standards were met. These principles guided the conduct of the study in a responsible and respectful manner, prioritizing the rights and well-being of the participants (Mack et al., 2005).

Respect for person. The ethical principle of respecting individuals underscores the significance of treating research participants with politeness and recognizing their autonomy in making decisions about their involvement in a study (Munhall, 2012 & Scott, 2013). This principle requires that participants are provided with comprehensive information about the study, ensuring they have a clear understanding of the research, including any potential risks or benefits. Obtaining informed consent is a pivotal aspect of upholding this principle, as it represents a voluntary agreement based on well-informed comprehension. By adhering to the respect for person's principle, the researcher can ensure that the study is conducted in an ethical manner that upholds the rights and autonomy of the participants.

Prior to commencing the interviews, the researcher sought participants' consent and coordinated schedules in advance to prevent any conflicts with their academic commitments or other obligations. This proactive approach aimed to ensure minimal disruption to the participants' schedules and avoided the need for interview rescheduling or cancellations.

Throughout the conduct of the study, the researcher fostered a respectful and polite relationship with the participants, obtaining their consent before recording any conversations. Participants were encouraged to pose questions at any point, and the confidentiality of in-depth interviews and group discussions was maintained. Furthermore, participants retained the right to decline answering sensitive questions. By building rapport and displaying courtesy toward the participants, the research was conducted in an ethical and considerate manner.

Social Value. This entails assessing whether the research addresses important societal problems or needs, benefits marginalized or vulnerable populations, or advances knowledge in a meaningful way. Recognizing social value requires researchers to critically evaluate the potential impact of their work on individuals and communities, aiming for outcomes that promote societal well-being and equity. By prioritizing social value, researchers uphold ethical principles and contribute to the responsible conduct of research (Resnik, 2015).

This study was aiming to determine the level of motivational orientation in learning English among BEED students. The method for data collection was comprehensively clarified in order to gather broad feedback from the participants, the primary objective of the analysis. The research results were presented to the participants and shared with the public. Additionally, the researcher demonstrated a strong commitment to the integrity of the convergent parallel mixed methods design employed in this study, thereby upholding the ethical principle of social value in research.

Informed Consent. Obtaining consent stands as a foundational element of research ethics, signifying respect for research participants (Creswell, 2012). In securing informed consent, the participants gained a comprehensive understanding of the research's objectives and purpose, ensuring transparency in their involvement. Written consent was acquired from the participants, affirming their willingness to engage in in-depth interviews and group discussions while providing them with insights into the study's outcomes and discoveries.

To uphold the study's ethical standards, the researcher furnished the participants with permission and consent letters, elucidating the study's details, methodologies, design, and procedures (Creswell, 2012). These documents aimed to aid participants in comprehending the study's nature, facilitating informed decision-making about their participation. Those who chose not to participate were free to withdraw without providing reasons, with an assurance of the confidentiality of their data. Furthermore, participants were informed of their right to be informed of the study's results. Adhering to these ethical principles, the researcher ensured that the study was conducted responsibly and respectfully.

Vulnerability of the Research Participants. The study participants in this research were not vulnerable in any way. They were the students of Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology. Thus, in this study, vulnerable participants were given the greatest attention and caution. In addition, participants were scheduled to respond to the survey questionnaire based on their period and time availability.

The Risks, Benefits and Safety. Beneficence, as an ethical principle, underscores the dedication to mitigate risks and enhance the well-being of research participants (Bricki & Green, 2007). In this study, deliberate measures were taken to ensure the safety and safeguarding of the participants. The interviewees' identities were kept anonymous to safeguard their privacy and confidentiality. All information files were securely stored and never left unattended or unprotected.

In alignment with the principle of beneficence, the researcher prioritized the anonymity and confidentiality of participants' responses and personal details. Physical risks were averted by selecting a secure location conducive to their safety. As a token of goodwill, participants may receive gifts, materials, or goods to acknowledge their valuable contribution to the study. These actions demonstrate the researcher's commitment to ethical research practices and the well-being of the participants.

Furthermore, the data collected in this research study will be strictly used for the purposes outlined. Nevertheless, the study's results may also be disseminated through various channels, such as presentations within the institution, publication in scientific forums or journals, or presentations at conferences, whether at local, national, or international levels. Through this dissemination, the researcher aims to share findings and contribute to the broader knowledge base within their field of study.

Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. In upholding confidentiality for data, results, and findings while safeguarding participants, various techniques were employed (Maree & Westhuizen, 2007). This involved concealing the personal identities of the participants, ensuring that no such information was disclosed. All materials, including audio records, coded transcripts, notes, as well as digital and physical data copies, will be securely disposed of once the data analysis is completed.

To protect participants' identities and adhere to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researcher utilized discrete coding to represent each participant's responses. This approach entails carefully phrasing any information that might potentially reveal the participants' identity, such as their name, gender, ethnicity, or employment/location, to maintain their anonymity. Through the use of effective coding and other precautionary measures, the researcher safeguarded participants' identities and respect their privacy.

Justice. Justice in conducting this study revolved around respecting the rights of participants who identified themselves as BEED-Generalist students. Since the study aimed to investigate the motivational orientation of BEED students in learning English, no minors' rights were infringed upon. To ensure fairness and equal opportunity for participation, the researcher employed both random and purposive sampling techniques. BEED- Generalist students were not coerced into participation and retained the freedom to decline at their discretion. As a recognition of their valuable contribution, tokens were provided to the participants, duly acknowledging their involvement in the research and contributing to the overall success of the study. Moreover, justice was maintained by including only relevant remarks from the participants related to the research objectives and ensuring accurate transcription (Munhall, 2012 & Scott, 2013).

Transparency. This study adhered to the ideals of transparency by completely informing the participants that the study concentrated on the motivational orientation on learning English among BEED students. It is the researcher's responsibility to be just and fair in the conduct of this study. In addition, participants will be presented with interview notes and transcribed documents for confirmation and approval. Therefore, the results of the study were shared with the respondents and participants.

Qualification of the Researchers. The researcher was reliable and credible to conduct this study, a survey on motivational orientation on learning English among BEED students. The researcher is a third-year college student taking up the program of Bachelor of Elementary Education - Generalist and attempted to conduct this study in pursuit of self-enhancements and as per research development.

Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher ensured that there were existing and available resources needed in this institutional study. Online journals, periodicals, magazines, books and unpublished dissertations are available for further understandings and references which provided various literatures and readings that supported the connotation of the variables used in the study. In this study, adequate facilities were provided such as laptop and cellphone for the accuracy of collecting data from the participants during the conduct.

Community Involvement. During the initial presentation of this study, community leaders, faculty and students were invited during the Public Forum which could be done through virtual meetings and presentation. This research generated awareness, and implications were given to the school administrators and instructors based on the survey of the level of motivational orientation in learning English among BEED students. This study was useful for the technical research committee, the conference managers, and journal publishers who helped disseminate the results of the study to provide additional information and deeper understanding of the level of motivational orientation in learning English among BEED students.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the results of the study based on the analysis of the quantitative and qualitative data. The presentation of quantitative results started with the descriptive result which presents on the motivational orientation on learning English among BEED students. Consequently, the presentation of the qualitative phase follows which included the thematic analysis of the lived experiences, coping mechanism, and insights shared regarding the motivational orientation on learning English among BEED students.

Level of BEED Students' Motivational Orientation on Learning English

Table 2 presents the level of BEED student's motivational orientation on learning English in Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology in terms of their extrinsic orientation, international orientation, and intrinsic orientation. The results show that the overall mean is 4.42 with a description of very high it shows that the motivational orientation on learning English in terms of extrinsic orientation is always manifested by the BEED students. The highest mean is item number 4 it will allow me to get good grades of English in school with the mean of 4.52 with a description of very high which means that it is always manifested by the BEED students.

Table 2. Level of BEED Student's Motivational Orientation on Learning English

<i>No. Items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
Extrinsic Orientation		
1 In the era of globalization I need English.	4.42	Very High
2 It will allow me to have access to information written in English.	4.49	Very High
3 It will allow me to get a job.	4.45	Very High
4 It will allow me to get good scores of English in school.	4.52	Very High
5 I want to master foreign language.	4.23	High
	Category Mean 4.42	Very High
International Orientation		
1 It will allow me to meet with more speakers of English.	4.39	Very High
2 It will allow me to participate more freely in the activities of speakers of English.	4.46	Very High
3 It will allow me to gain good friends more easily among speakers of English.	4.13	High
4 It will enable me to better understand the cultures of speakers of	4.53	Very High

English.		
5	It will allow me to learn more about the culture and art of English-speaking countries.	4.47 Very High
		Category Mean 4.40 Very High
Intrinsic Orientation		
1	I like English.	4.00 High
2	I enjoy learning foreign language.	4.13 High
3	Mastering English makes me confident.	4.20 High
4	I want to improve my English for travelling.	4.40 Very High
5	I enjoy the satisfaction when I find out new things in English.	4.39 Very High
		Category Mean 4.22 High
		Overall Mean 4.35 Very High

In contrast, item number 5 I want to master foreign language got the lowest mean of 4.23 with a description of high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the BEED students in terms of their extrinsic orientation.

Moreover, it is also shown on the table that the motivational orientation on learning English among BEED students in terms of their international orientation got a description of very high with a mean of 4.40 which means that the BEED student’s motivational orientation on learning English in terms of international orientation is always manifested. Item number 4 it will enable me to understand the cultures of speaker of English got the highest mean of 4.53 with a description of very high which means that it is always manifested by the BEED students. On the other hand, the lowest mean is 4.13 for item number 3 it will allow me gain good friends more easily among speakers of English with a description of high which means that motivational orientation on learning English is oftentimes manifested by the BEED students in terms of their international orientation.

Finally, the motivational orientation on learning English among BEED students in terms of their intrinsic orientation is oftentimes manifested with an overall mean of 4.22 with a description of high. As shown on the table, item 4 I want to improve my English for travelling is always manifested by the BEED students with the highest mean of 4.40 with a description of very high. In contrast, the lowest mean is item number 2 I enjoy learning foreign language with a mean of 4.13 with a description of high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the BEED students.

The Lived Experiences and Challenges of BEED Students on their Motivational Orientation on Learning English

There were three essential themes drawn from the responses of the participants in the in-depth interview and focus group discussion on the first research question. Presented in Table 3 are the responses of the participants regarding their lived experiences and challenges with their motivational orientation on learning English, they are experiencing difficulty in language learning and language use, having fear of judgement resulting to lack of self- confidence, and struggling with external pressure in achieving competence of language use.

Table 3. *The Lived Experiences and Challenges of BEED Students on their Motivational Orientation on Learning English*

ISSUES PROBED	CORE IDEAS	CODE/ CATEGORIES	ESSENTIAL THEMES	THEORETICAL SUPPORT
Academic Challenges towards English Language Proficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> English grammar is complex due to its numerous rules and exceptions, which can sometimes be overwhelming and difficult to internalize. Difficulty in grammar, trust issues with spelling, and occasional difficulty pronouncing words Facing numerous difficulties while learning English, including learning terminologies, 	Struggles with Grammar, Spelling, and Pronunciation	Experiencing Difficulty in Language Learning and Language Use	Cognitive Load Theory

	<p>spelling, and pronunciation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feeling intimidated or embarrassed to speak English fluently because of concerns about pronunciation • Using the first language on a daily basis can lead to limited exposure to the English language 	<p>Lack of Mastery in Speaking English due to Linguistic Background</p>		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty in organizing and delivering impromptu ideas effectively to an audience or the public • Fear of constructing English sentences due to potential errors or misunderstandings • Struggle to express ideas or opinions effectively due to difficulties in using the English language, fear of speaking up and being conscious of potential mistakes or misused words • Difficulty in expressing oneself confidently in English despite having ideas 	<p>Difficulties in Constructing and Delivering Ideas using English Language</p>		
<p>Psychological and Social Pressures in</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fear of speaking in front of many people due to the concern of being judged by others • Fear of making grammar mistakes and being judged by classmates or others, leading to hesitation in committing to speaking • Anxiety about speaking English, whether in front of others or not 	<p>Performance Anxiety in English Communication due to Fear of Judgement</p>	<p>Having Fear of</p>	

<p>English Communication Arise from Fear of Judgment and Lack of Confidence</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty in speaking English, particularly in front of listeners, due to the fear of judgment based on speech patterns and grammar. • Low self-confidence leads to speaking in the vernacular language instead of English • Limited confidence contributes to difficulties in speaking English effectively • Internal motivation is affected by low self-confidence and self-esteem, particularly when required to speak English in front of others • Struggling with fluency in English creates a sense of embarrassment and pressure 	<p>Lack of Confidence in Using English Language</p>	<p>Judgement Resulting to Lack of Self-Confidence</p>	<p>Affective Filter Hypothesis</p>
<p>Influence of External Pressures on Learning English Language</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education students encounter significant societal pressure to succeed, as even minor errors in pronunciation or grammar can escalate the expectation placed on them, given their future role as educators • Facing pressure from others to meet high English proficiency expectations results in unnecessary stress and strain. • Being expected to excel in English communication skills influences external motivation levels. 	<p>Pressure due to Heightened Expectations of Others in Achieving Competence of Language Use</p>	<p>Struggling with External Pressure</p>	<p>Affective Filter Hypothesis</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Under pressure from teachers and classmates because they excel in English • Feeling pressured when interacting with others who are fluent in English • Consistency of high proficiency in English demonstrated by teachers and classmates affects one's perception of language skills. 	<p>Experienced Comparisons Among Other Students</p>		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The pressure and demotivation can arise when instructors persist in expecting responses in English • The pressure of giving response in English when being asked 	<p>Language Proficiency Pressure in Education</p>		

Experiencing Difficulty in Language Learning and Language Use. Taking into consideration the information and data gathered as shared by the participants through in-depth interview and focus group discussion, majority of the BEED students are experiencing difficulty in language learning and language use that affects their motivation on learning English.

Struggles with Grammar, Spelling, and Pronunciation. This is the first code on the first probed issue. Students expressed common responses on their experiences on English language learning. Most of them stated that they are struggling with grammar, spelling, and pronunciation that affects their motivation on learning English.

During the interview, it came to light that students are facing challenges with the complexity of English grammar. Learnstar (pseudonym) articulated that intricacy of English grammar, with its multitude of rules and exceptions, can be overwhelming and difficult to grasp. The complexity of these grammatical nuances often creates confusion and frustration, making it challenging to master the language. This feeling of being overwhelmed can hinder one's progress and confidence in using English effectively. She conveyed that:

“Kanang sa grammar complexity or ang English man gud kay daghan kaayo siya’g mga rules and exceptions so mura’g ma overwhelmed ko ba kay mura’g libog kaayo usahay niya dili dayun nimo siya ma internalize.” (IDI- 03)

(The grammar complexity in English can be overwhelming due to its numerous rules and exceptions, making it sometimes difficult to internalize quickly.)

Additionally, students are encountering challenges with grammar and spelling, revealing a common struggle faced by many individuals. They express a lack of confidence in their ability to spell words correctly, which reflects their trust issues with spelling, as noted by Focusbright (pseudonym). She elaborated that:

“Maglisod ko usahay sa grammar, tapos naa pud koy trust issues sa spelling og usahay pud kanang bulol ko usahay so maglisud ko ug pronounce.” (IDI-01)

(Sometimes, I struggle with grammar, and I also have trust issues with spelling. Sometimes, I stumble over my words and find it difficult to pronounce them correctly.)

Similarly, Wordchaser (pseudonym) encountered various challenges while learning English, particularly when it comes to mastering terminology, spelling, and pronunciation. Many English words have complex spellings that don't always align with their pronunciation, making it difficult to remember the correct forms. She remarked that:

“There are a lot of difficulties that I have faced in learning English and one of this is kining mga ano gud terminologies, ang spelling tapos ang kining pronunciation.” (IDI-02)

(I have faced a lot of difficulties in learning English, especially with terminology, spelling, and pronunciation.)

Lack of Mastery in Speaking English due to Linguistic Background. The participants highlighted that their lack of fluency in speaking English, stemming from their linguistic backgrounds, poses a significant challenge that impacts their motivation to learn the language. Here are their perspectives:

In the interview, Learnstar (pseudonym) expresses a deep-seated insecurity related to her pronunciation, which stems from the fact that she is not a native English speaker. This language barrier often leads her to feel intimidated or embarrassed when speaking English, as she fears stumbling over words or mispronouncing them. This sentiment reflects her perspective:

“The way pud nimo siya I pronounce gud, ing ana mura’g ma bidlian ka kay dili biya ta native speaker sa ano no so para sa akua mura’g ma ano ko ana mura’g ma intimidate oh maulaw ko mo speak through that language kay mura’g feel nako ma bulol ko.” (IDI-03)

(The way you pronounce it can also make you feel insecure because we are not native English speakers, so for me I feel intimidated or embarrassed to speak through that language because I feel like I might stumble.)

Similarly, Languageheart (pseudonym) faces the challenge of limited exposure to the English language, largely due to the daily use of her first language, Bisaya. This limited interaction with English hinders her progress in becoming more fluent, as she don’t get enough practice or immersion in the language. She articulated that:

“The first language that I know is bisaya gud siya naanad ko nga mag bisaya everytime nga mag storya sa mga tao nga makasalamuha kay dili mani sila mga American.” (FGD-01)

(Bisaya is the first language I learned, so I am used to speaking it every time I talk to people, I interact with, especially because they are not Americans.)

Difficulties in Constructing and Delivering Ideas using English Language. This is the third code of the probed issue. Participants acknowledged that they struggle with formulating and articulating ideas in English, which hinders their participation in class discussions. Here are their collective reflections:

In the interview, it emerged that Fluentdream (pseudonym) struggles with organizing her thoughts and delivering impromptu responses effectively, especially in public settings or when addressing an audience. This difficulty adds to her anxiety when speaking English, as the pressure to think and respond quickly can overwhelm her. She expressed that:

“Unsaon nako pag construct akoang ideas unsaon nako pag deliver kanang mga impromptu nga kanang mga questions unsaon nako pag deliver og tarong akoang mga ideas in front, sa mga audience, og sa public.” (IDI- 07)

(How will I construct my ideas, how will I deliver impromptu responses to questions and how can I effectively present my ideas in front of an audience and the public.)

Furthermore, Leximind (pseudonym) faces the challenge of fearing to construct English sentences due to the possibility of errors or misunderstandings, which could lead to embarrassment. She expressed apprehension about making mistakes that could potentially embarrass her, stating:

“Ma hadlok ko mo construct og English kay basin mali wala nagka dimao.” (IDI-05)

(I am afraid to construct English sentences because I might make mistakes and feel embarrassed.)

Similarly, Wordchaser (pseudonym) grapples with expressing her ideas and opinions effectively because of difficulties with English language usage. This struggle leads to hesitation when speaking up, as she fears making mistakes or misusing words. The anxiety of potentially being misunderstood or judged for their language errors creates a barrier that prevents them from fully participating in conversations.

She states that:

“Dili nako matarong og express ang akoang idea or opinion kay tungod maglisud ko og English maglisud ko ug gamit og English language so mao to mahadlok nako mutingog dili nalang ko mo tingog kay ma conscious naman ko ug unsa pay ma storya ba basin mamali mali pa ang mga words nga ipang ingon.” (IDI-02)

(I struggle to express my ideas or opinions because I find it difficult to use the English language. I am afraid to speak up because I become self-conscious and worry that I might use the wrong words or make mistakes.)

Moreover, Learnstar (pseudonym) also encounters the challenge of struggling to express herself confidently, even when she has clear ideas. The difficulty lies in articulating her thoughts in English, which often results in a lack of clarity when trying to convey her ideas effectively. She articulated:

“Dili ko hawd, dili nako ma express akoang kaugalingon ba pag mag English ko although naa kay mga idea pero need man siya ikuaan ug English so mao na maglisud ko sauna so hantud karun maglisud gud gihapon.” (IDI- 03)

(I find it challenging to express myself when speaking English, even though I have ideas. However, since English is required, I struggle to convey my thoughts effectively. This difficulty persists, making it hard for me until now.)

Having Fear of Judgement Resulting to Lack of Self-Confidence. This is the second essential theme drawn from the responses of participants from in-depth interview and focus group discussion. When core ideas and categories were analyzed and synthesized, it reveals that students are having psychological and social pressures in English communication arise from fear of judgement and lack of confidence affecting their motivation to learn the language.

Performance Anxiety in English Communication due to Fear of Judgement. This is the first code of the issue that was probed. The participants shared that they are having anxiety with regards to their performance in English communication due to fear of being judged. For them, they are afraid of committing mistakes particularly in using English language because they think they will be judged by those other people surrounds them.

During the interview, *Fluentdream* (pseudonym) mentioned that she is afraid of speaking in front of many people due to the concern of being judged by others. She knows that Filipinos are very particular about grammar and vocabularies and that a small mistake can lead to being judged. She stated that:

“Mahadlok man gud ko mag speak sa in front of many people and I’m afraid to be judged and since we all know that Filipinos are very particular with grammar and vocabularies gamay lang gani nimong mali miskan sa pag pronounce kay ijudge na dayun ka nila.” (IDI-07)

(I am really afraid to speak in front of many people, and I am scared of being judged, especially since Filipinos are very particular about grammar and vocabularies. Even a small mistake in pronunciation can lead to being judged.)

Similarly, *Leximind* (pseudonym) experiences the fear of being judged by others due to making grammar mistakes, which leads to hesitation in committing to speak in English. This anxiety creates a barrier to open communication, as she worries that her errors might be criticized or misunderstood. As she revealed in the interview that:

“Mahadlok ko maka commit ug mistake when it comes to grammar kay basin ma judge ko sa akoang mga classmates or sa uban tao.” (IDI-05)

(I am afraid of making mistakes in grammar because I might be judged by my classmates or other people.)

In addition, *Studyglow* (pseudonym) experiences anxiety about speaking English, whether in front of others or in more private settings, due to a constant fear of being judged by those around her. This pervasive sense of being scrutinized makes her self-conscious about her language skills, which exacerbates her hesitation to speak. In her interview, she said:

“Mahadlok ko mag storya ug English especially sa front or bisan dili ko sa front basta kay mag storya ko kay feeling nako kay gina judge ko sa mga tao.” (FGD-02)

(I am afraid to speak English, especially in front of others or even just in conversation, because I feel like I am being judged by people.)

Furthermore, it was being expressed by *Knowquest* (pseudonym) during the interview that she has difficulty speaking English, especially in front of listeners, due to a fear of judgment based on her speech patterns and grammar. This concern about making mistakes or being critiqued leads to significant anxiety, which affects her confidence and ability to express herself clearly. She stated that:

“One of the difficulties that I have faced in learning English is that speaking in front especially if there are some people who listen to me because I think they will judge me on the way I spoke or the grammar that I used.” (FGD- 03)

(One of the difficulties I have faced in learning English is speaking in front of others, especially when there are people listening, as I fear that they will judge me based on my pronunciation or grammar usage.)

Lack of Confidence in Using English Language. This is the second code of the issue probed. The participants from in-depth interview and focus group discussion imparted that they have a lack of confidence in using the English language, this affects their overall experience in learning the language. Because of this reason, the participants are experiencing demotivation towards learning the English.

It was stated by *Fluentdream* (pseudonym) during the interview that she experiences low self-confidence in speaking English, which leads her to choose the vernacular language over English. This lack of confidence stems from fears of making mistakes or being judged, prompting her to default to a language in which she feels more comfortable and secure. She mentioned that:

“Low akoang self-confidence so mao nang kung mag speak ko in front of many people kay dili nalang English akoang ginagamit kay gagamit nalang ko og vernacular language.” (IDI-07)

(Due to my low self-confidence when speaking in front of many people, I tend to use my vernacular language instead of English.)

Similarly, according to Wordchaser (pseudonym) limited confidence further contributes to her difficulties in speaking English effectively, particularly when addressing a large audience. The pressure of performing in front of many people exacerbates her anxiety, making it even harder to communicate clearly and confidently. She stated that:

“Gamay ko ug confidence gani kay dili jud ko ingon nga enhance sa English maong naa jud koy difficulties sa mag storya nga in English labi na ug daghan kaayo ug tao mao na akoang difficulties.” (FGD-05)

(Because of my lack of confidence, I struggle to improve my English skills, which leads to difficulties when speaking in English, especially in front of a large audience.)

Moreover, Fluentdream (pseudonym) claimed that her internal motivation to learn English is significantly affected by her low self-confidence, especially when she is required to speak English in front of others. The fear of making mistakes or being judged in such situations diminishes her enthusiasm and willingness to practice, leading to a decreased drive to improve her English skills. She mentioned that:

“Ang naka affect sa akoang motivation internally kay akoang low of self-confidence og self-esteem kay parehas aning sa room lang naa miy isa ka subject nga required me mo speak og English since our instructor believes na gamit kaayo siya in the future and as a future educator so kay low man akoang self-confidence and self-esteem to speak in front of many people dijud nako malikayan nga makagamit jud ko og vernacular language.” (IDI-07)

(The Internal factors affecting my motivation include my low self-confidence and self-esteem. This is particularly challenging when I have to speak English in front of a large group, especially when I lack confidence. It is difficult for me to avoid resorting to using my vernacular language in such situations.)

Furthermore, Studyglow (pseudonym) mentioned during the interview that the struggles in fluency in English that she encounters creates a sense of embarrassment and pressure for her because she has this constant feeling that she is being left behind by others and that it is difficult for her to catch up. In her interview, she revealed:

“Mura’g ulaw kaayo sa akoo kung ay so dili ko fluent sa English so mag learn na ug English language so kanang mura’g ulaw ba nga kanang dugay nani gina learn tas dugay gihapon ka catch up.” (FGD-02)

(It feels quite embarrassing for me if I am not fluent in English, especially when learning the language. It is like a constant feeling of being behind and struggling to catch up, which can be really daunting.)

Struggling with External Pressure. Another essential theme drawn from the responses of the participants is their struggles with external pressure in achieving competence of language use, this pressure affects their motivation on learning the language. The participants mentioned that the expectations given by others put pressure to them as they are expected to excel in English.

Pressure due to Heightened Expectations of Others in Achieving Competence of Language Use. This is the first code of the third probed issue. The participants shared that they experienced pressure due to heightened expectations from others. Being an education student, they are expected to have mastery in English. Even the slightest error in English can escalate the expectation placed on them. As expressed by Focusbright (pseudonym):

“Kining expectation jud sa atoa as educ student kay once man gud ug mo ingon na kining education student ka, taas kaayo na’g expectation ang tao sa imoha kay syempre maestra nagud ka, ikaw mo tudlo pag mamabantayan lang gani na nga mamali lang ka ug pronounce or naa lang jud kay mali sa grammar kataw an naman gani na so kana ang grabe ang pressure sa amoa ana kanang mga expectations sa tao nga dapat pag educ student ka dapat jud bright ka.” (IDI-01)

(The expectations placed on us as education students are quite high. Once people know you are an education student, they have lofty expectations because, of course, you are going to be a teacher, expected to teach and be meticulous in grammar and pronunciation. The pressure from those expectations is immense; it is expected that as education students, we should be exceptionally bright.)

Moreover, as expressed by Wordchaser (pseudonym) during the interview that facing pressure from others to meet high English proficiency expectations results in unnecessary stress and strain. The constant demand to perform at a certain level can overwhelm her, exacerbating her anxiety and making it even more challenging to use English effectively. She mentioned that:

“Dili jud malikayan nato ang mga tao no nga mag kuaan ang expectation nila sa atoa ba labi na kay kini college students nata tapos especially as BEED student nga dapat hawud ka mo pronounce hawud ka sa English, mga tao nga kusog kaayo muhatag bitaw sa imoha og pressure, mura’g ma pressure naka ba nga dapat perfect imohang pag English ing ana.” (IDI-02)

(It is unavoidable that people will have high expectations of us, especially as college students and particularly as BEED students who are expected to excel in pronunciation and English proficiency. People can be quite insistent in putting pressure on us, making it feel like we must be perfect in our English.)

Furthermore, the expectation to excel in public speaking and communication skills places significant external pressure. This pressure heavily influences her learning of English, often exacerbating anxiety and impacting her confidence, as being expressed by Fluentdream

(pseudonym) during her interview:

“I’m a future educator I am expected to be good at speaking in front of many people hawd ta og communication skills and so mao to mao to ang maka affect sa akua externally in terms sa pag learn nako og English.” (IDI- 07)

(As a future educator, there is an expectation for me to excel in public speaking and communication skills. This external pressure significantly affects my learning of English.)

Experienced Comparisons Among Other Students. It is the second code of the issue that was probed. The participants shared that they experienced comparison among other students. The participants shared that they are under pressure from teachers and classmates because they excel in English. As conveyed by Languageheart (pseudonym):

“Ma pressure ko sa mga teachers like that and also sa akoang mga classmates ana gud kay makaingon ka kanang hala mga fluent kaayo sila mag English unlike sa akua nga oh my gosh kanang mga carabao carabao rajud ni siya nga English.” (FGD-01)

(I feel pressured by teachers and classmates who are fluent in English. It is disheartening when others seem effortlessly fluent, while I struggle and feel like my English is very basic in comparison.)

Additionally, Leximind (pseudonym) said during the interview that she feels pressured whenever interacting with other students who are fluent in English. This pressure makes her anxious, as she worries about whether she can match their proficiency. The comparison heightens her self-doubt and stress, impacting her ability to engage confidently in conversations and affecting her overall learning experience. She mentioned that:

“Pressure pud sa uban tao kay makakita nako sila nga labaw na kung maka maka naa koy maka atubang nga kaila nako nga fluent kaayo mo storya og English ma pressure ko maka hunahuna ko og what if kaya ing ato pud ko.” (IDI-05)

(I also feel pressure from others, especially when they see me interact with someone, I know who is fluent in English. It makes me anxious, thinking about whether I can do the same or not.)

Furthermore, Readspark (pseudonym) stated during the interview that the consistency of high proficiency demonstrated by teachers and classmates affects her perception of language skills. Every time she interacts with others who speaks English very well, she feels pressured to do the same. She stated that:

“People around me especially the teachers and the classmates so if kanang everytime nga makadungong ko sa ilaha nga hawd kaayo sila mag speak ug English.” (FGD-04)

(People around me especially teachers and classmates who speak English very well. Every time I hear them speak, I feel the pressure to do the same.)

Language Proficiency Pressure in Education. It is the third code of the issue that was probed. The participants shared that they experienced language proficiency pressure in education. The participants shared that they felt demotivated when the instructors persist them to respond in English. As expressed by Languageheart (pseudonym):

“Sa mga instructors nga kanang ma pressure ka kay kanang muingon sila nga everytime nga mag talk ka mo response ka sa ako dapat English tapos ikaw nga ikaw mismo ako mismo nga dijud ko ingon nga fluent ana nga diraa nga dapit tapos ikana ganing ipressure ka anang maka maka kanang makababa gud siya sa imohang motivation kay kanang kabalo naman ka kung asa ka dapit nga limitation.” (FGD-01)

(It is challenging when instructors put pressure on you to respond in English every time you speak, especially when you do not feel fluent in that language. This pressure can really affect your motivation, especially when you are aware of your limitations.)

Similarly, Studyglow (pseudonym) expressed during the interview that she felt pressure when giving response in English when being asked. She expressed that giving responses in English is very challenging because she is not fluent in using the language. She stated that:

“When they ask question gusto nila nga kay ang itubag kay English language so niya sa akua nga dili jud fluent sa English so mura’g kuaan jud sa akua nga kung dili nako na matarong or dili nako na ma kuaan ang English kanang feeling nako kay baba nagud kaayo mao nay naka kuaan sad akua.” (FGD-02)

(When instructors ask questions, they expect responses in English, which can be challenging if you are not fluent. It feels like they are taking something away from you, making you feel inadequate when you can not articulate yourself well in English.)

The Coping Mechanism of BEED Students with Regards to their Motivational Orientation on Learning English

Displayed in Table 4 are the responses of the participants in regards to their coping mechanism to their motivational orientation on learning English. There are four essential themes which are drawn out from the in- depth interview and focus group discussion of the participants for the second question. Those are applying holistic approaches to enhance English proficiency, overcoming external

pressure through self-encouragement, improving one’s language proficiency through language exposure, and employing collaborative learning and technological support. The essential themes in this study were based on the issues being probed which were summarized on the table.

Table 4. *The Coping Mechanisms of BEED Students with Regards to the Challenges in Motivational Orientation on Learning*

ISSUES PROBED	CORE IDEAS	CATEGORIES/ CODES	ESSENTIAL THEMES	THEORETICAL SUPPORT
Availability of English movies and books to fosters language proficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Employing English movies and books to motivate oneself in enhancing language proficiency Engaging with English movies for listening practice and reading English books Refers to a dictionary to grasp the meanings of unfamiliar words and concepts 	Watching Movies and Reading Books as tools in Learning English	Applying Holistic Approaches to Enhance English Proficiency	Self-Determination Theory
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reading books aloud to improve the pronunciation of words Consuming English media motivates to keep learning the language as it unlocks more opportunities 			
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> When encountering challenges, relax, then shift focus once feeling better Incorporate short breaks into study sessions to prevent a decrease in motivation and maintain momentum in learning 	Taking Breaks to Maintain Motivation		
Recognizing Societal Expectations as Positive Incentives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> External pressures and societal expectations serve as incentives for excelling in English language studies. Adverse encounters have acted as a driving force to bolster confidence in English usage and to propel personal growth through learning. 	External Forces as Motivation for English Language Learning	Overcoming External Pressure through Self-Encourage-ment	Self-Determination Theory
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Opting to perceive those adverse experiences as motivation to further 	Overcoming Language Proficiency Challenges through		

	<p>their language learning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-encouragement persists despite encountering challenges and difficulties in learning the English language • Turning negative experiences into sources of motivation rather than discouragements 	<p>Self-Encouragement</p>		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Derives motivation and fulfillment from witnessing advancements in English proficiency • The acknowledgment of minor accomplishments acts as a catalyst for motivation • Acknowledging individual progress fuels the drive to persevere in one's endeavors 	<p>Celebrating Language Learning Progress with Positive Attitude</p>		
<p>Setting English Learning as one of the Priorities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effectively managing one's time while underlining it as a long-term investment • Placing studying as a top priority over other tasks • Allocating specific time slots for English study, involving activities like reading, practicing sentences, and watching movies to enhance vocabulary and language skills • Demonstrating a continual commitment to enhancing language proficiency • Establishing a regular study schedule tailored for English learning activities while fostering a structured routine for language practice • Making use of spare time to effectively study English 	<p>Doing Time Management for Language Learning</p>	<p>Improving One's Language Proficiency through Language Exposure and Setting Priorities</p>	<p>Goal-Setting Theory</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making use of spare time to effectively study English • Modifying daily routines and habits through employing time management 			
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Striving to establish realistic goals to enhance English proficiency and personal motivation • Establishing SMART objectives, breaking them down into manageable tasks, and consistently evaluating progress • Creating sequential objectives and modifying them if they prove unattainable within the designated timeframe 	Setting Goals for Language Learning		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhancing English pronunciation and fluency involves practicing in front of a mirror at home • Engaging in active practice and exerting effort to enhance English skills • Engaging in self-directed practice to refine pronunciation and ensure readiness for presentations, reports, and various activities 	Exposing Oneself to the Language Use		
Seeking guidance from peers fostering improvement in English proficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seeks help and clarification from friends and housemates concerning challenges in English language • Requesting help from friends to rectify errors in English grammar, sentence structure, and usage • Consistently seeks feedback from a skilled English-speaking friend/class-mate to refine English 	Value Support and Feedback provided by others	Employing Collaborative Learning and Technological Support	Sociocultural Theory

	speaking and writing abilities	Seeking Assistance on Language Learning through Technology		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dependence on technology in English learning and its impact on personal interaction • Utilization of technology, especially in seeking out unfamiliar words and maintaining motivation during English vocabulary acquisition • Integration of technology as the main approach to surmount challenges in learning English 			

Applying Holistic Approaches to Enhance English Proficiency. The coping mechanisms of the BEED students in accordance to their motivational orientation on learning English are being affected based from the similar responses given by the participants. Based on the information given by the participants, it is claimed that because of the experience they had regarding their motivational orientation on learning English they applied holistic approaches to enhance their English proficiency.

Watching Movies and Reading Books as Tools in Learning English. This is the first code for the first probed issue. Utilizing holistic approaches to enhance English proficiency involves integrating immersive activities such as watching movies and reading books. According to the participants, by incorporating both mediums, it fosters a comprehensive and enjoyable learning experience that promotes fluency and proficiency in English language skills.

Likewise, utilizing English films and literature can act as a catalyst for improving language skills. By engaging in movie watching and book reading, Wordchaser (pseudonym) finds herself more motivated to learn the language, noting improvements in comprehension and pronunciation. She expressed:

“By watching movies, by reading books kana nga nga pamaagi mura’g gina encourage na nako akoang self nga dapat ay mutan aw nalang ko’g kining mga movies nga English para nga naa koy makuha nga mga words or terminologies sa kato nga mga salida para nga naa pa koy makat onan and sa reading para nga ma enhance pud ang akoang comprehension, reading comprehension mga unsay tawag ani mga pronunciation ana.” (IDI-02)

(By watching movies and reading books in English, I am encouraging myself to learn. I make it a point to watch English movies to pick up new words and terminologies, and I read to enhance my reading comprehension and pronunciation skills.)

Additionally, by engaging with English movies, Leximind (pseudonym) finds it amusing to listen to the fluent pronunciation of the actors. Reading books serves as a motivation for her to further enhance her English skills. The exposure to well-articulated English through movies and the inspirational content of books helps her appreciate the language more and encourages her to continue improving her proficiency. She states that:

“Pag makatan aw ko og kana gong mga English movie, ganahan kaayo ko ma minaw sa the way sila mag pronounce fluently sa and then naga basa ko og mga books nga English para mas ma enhance pa ang akoang English, akoang speaking or ang kining pagtuon nako sa English karun.” (IDI-05)

(When I watch English movies, I enjoy listening to the fluent pronunciation, and when I read English books, it further enhances my English skills. This helps me improve my speaking and overall English learning process.)

Furthermore, Fluent (pseudonym) articulated that consulting a dictionary to comprehend unfamiliar words and concepts proves to be an effective strategy for enriching her vocabulary. By referencing the dictionary for unfamiliar words, he finds it aids in familiarizing himself with them and deepening her understanding. He remarked:

“Kanang mag basa ko og mga parehas anang dictionary gina tan aw nako ang mga kuaan og unsa ang mga meaning para masulod pud sa akoang hunahuna ba matiman an nako kanang mga words nga dili kaayo familiar sa akoga ginatiman an nako.” (IDI-04)

(I read dictionaries, I look up unfamiliar words to understand their meanings better and to remember them. This helps me familiarize myself with words that are not yet part of my vocabulary.)

In addition, Wordchaser (pseudonym) employs the strategy of reading books aloud to enhance her pronunciation of words. By vocalizing the text during her reading sessions, she actively practices and refines her pronunciation skills. This approach helps her gain better control over her articulation and improves her overall fluency in English. She noted:

“Kanang nagabasa ko og mga libro ginabasa jud nako siya ug kusog para nga mabasa jud nako akoang baba ba sa mga pronunciation sa mga words.” (IDI-02)

(I read books aloud to practice pronouncing words correctly.)

Furthermore, engaging with English media serves as a motivating factor for Learnstar (pseudonym) to continue her language learning journey, as it opens up more opportunities for her. She takes pleasure in reading books and watching movies because they expose her to a diverse range of vocabularies. She stated:

“Ganahan man gud ko mag tan aw og mga movies, kanang mag basa basa og libro niya daghan biya kaayo na’g mga kuaan no ang kadalasan biya sa mga libro kay naa may mga English pud niya ganahan pud ko mag kuaan ana kanang mao sad nay maka motivate sa akoo nga kuaan maglearn pa og English kay pag maka learn ka og English it.” (IDI-03)

(I enjoy watching movies and reading books because they expose me to a variety of vocabulary. Many books include English, which motivates me to continue learning English because mastering it opens up many opportunities)

Taking Breaks to Maintain Motivation. This is the second code for the first probed issue. The participants emphasize that taking breaks is another effective approach to maintaining motivation in the process of learning

English. Taking breaks is crucial for sustaining motivation because it allows individuals to recharge and prevent burnout. According to them, continuous engagement in any task can lead to fatigue and diminished enthusiasm over time. By incorporating breaks into the learning process, the participants can rejuvenate their energy levels, refresh their minds, and regain focus.

Wordchaser (pseudonym) mentions that when faced with difficulties while learning English, she takes a moment to unwind. After allowing herself time to relax, she redirects her attention and resumes learning once she feels more at ease and ready. This approach helps her manage stress and maintain a positive mindset, enabling her to continue her studies more effectively. She elaborated:

“So when facing difficulties in learning English akoang gina relax akong self then focus pag okay na then proceed napud ko.” (IDI-02)

(When facing difficulties in learning English, I relax myself and then focus. Once I feel okay, I proceed with my learning.)

Similarly, Studyglow (pseudonym) She incorporates short breaks, especially when facing challenges like learning English. After resting, she returns to her studies, which helps her maintain motivation and prevent burnout. This practice allows her to approach her learning with renewed energy and focus, enhancing her overall effectiveness and resilience. She states that:

“Kanang mag rest then after that mo balik ug study ana lang siya para dili siya makakuan sa motivation, mag go on gihapon siya sa motivation in learning.” (FGD-02)

(After taking a rest, I return to studying to maintain motivation and keep going in my learning journey.) **Overcoming External Pressure through Self-Encouragement.** The coping strategies of the BEED students, aligned with their motivational orientation towards learning English, appear to be influenced by similar responses from the participants. According to the information shared by the participants, self-encouragement serves as a powerful tool for overcoming external pressures by fostering resilience and bolstering confidence. By affirming their own capabilities and focusing on internal motivation, individuals can reduce the impact of external stressors on their learning journey.

External Forces as Motivation for English Language Learning. The first code of the second probed issue. As per the participants' perspectives, external pressure can function as a positive incentive for proficiency in the English language. Rather than succumbing to pressure, they advocate for leveraging it as motivation to sustain their enthusiasm throughout the learning process. This mindset encourages individuals to view challenges as opportunities for growth and continuous improvement in their English skills.

In line with this, Focusbright (pseudonym) shares that whenever faced with external or societal pressure, she refrains from succumbing to it. Instead, she chooses to perceive it as a driving force to excel further in her English language studies. This mindset allows her to transform pressure into motivation, helping her stay focused on improving her language skills rather than being discouraged by expectations. She stated that:

“Maka motivate lang jud sa akoo kay katong mga ginaingon nako ang pressure sa akoo as a BEED student katong mga judgements sa tao expectations nila mao lang jud to ang makapamotivate sa akoo sa pag learn sa English.” (IDI- 01)

(What motivates me is when I hear the pressure as a BEED student, the judgments of people, their expectations. Those are the things that really motivate me to learn English.)

Moreover, Leximind (pseudonym) highlights that adversities serve as a catalyst for enhancing confidence in English usage and fostering personal development through learning. Each instance of criticism or judgment she faces due to mistakes propels her to further her

language skills and cultivate self-assurance. She remarked:

“So as I mentioned earlier no nga naa juy judgement sa akoo so usahay ginakataw an ko pag ma mispronounced nako or ma mali ko og storya maka buhat ko og sentence nga mali makit an nila sa uban nakong mga kauban so kadto, mao to siyay nagtulak sa akoo nga mas mag learn, mas magtuon sa English and karun kay katong mga experience nga akoang naagian bisan painful to siya kay mao jud to siya ang gigamit nako nga para ipush nako akoang kaugalingon nga uhm to learn English and to be confident as well.” (IDI-05)

(As I mentioned earlier, there are judgments against me, so sometimes I am laughed at when I mispronounce or make mistakes in stories. I make wrong sentences, and others notice. That is what pushed me to learn more, to study English more. And now, those experiences I have been through, even if they were painful, they are what I use to push myself to learn English and to be confident as well.)

Overcoming Language Proficiency Challenges through Self-Encouragement. The second code of the second probed issue. According to the participants, self-encouragement plays a crucial role in overcoming language proficiency challenges they encounter. By affirming their own abilities and maintaining a positive mindset, they can navigate difficulties with greater resilience and determination.

Likewise, Fluentdream (pseudonym) articulates the choice to view adverse experiences as motivation to further her language learning journey. Each challenging encounter becomes an encouragement for her to persist in learning English, using difficulties as opportunities to strengthen her skills and determination. This positive outlook helps her stay resilient and committed to her language goals. She stated:

“So those experiences of mine kay wala nako siya gina serve as discouragement instead kay gi serve nako siya as my encouragement to learn the language more.” (IDI-07)

(Instead of letting those experiences discourage me, I use them as encouragement to continue learning the language.)

Moreover, self-encouragement aids Wordchaser (pseudonym) in persevering through challenges and obstacles encountered in learning the English language. Rather than allowing these challenges to deter her, she reinforces her belief in her ability to master the language through positive self-affirmations. She stated:

“Gina encourage lang nako akoang kaugalingon nga kaya nako ni despite sa mga challenges nga akoang na encounter, akoo nalang gina gaslight akoang kaugalingon nga, paghilom namo, akoo nalang gina gaslight akoang kaugalingon nga kaya nako ni despite sa mga difficulties nga akoang na encounter in learning English language.” (IDI-02)

(I encourage myself to believe that I can overcome the challenges I encounter in learning the English language. Instead of letting them discourage me, I affirm to myself that I am capable of mastering English despite the difficulties I face.)

Moreover, Focusbright (pseudonym) reveals that whenever confronted with adverse experiences, she harnesses them as sources of motivation to confront and overcome negativity. Instead of allowing them to discourage her, she transforms them into opportunities for encouragement and motivation to further her language learning journey. She mentioned that:

“Katong mga experience nga atoang na encounter while kining gina kita nga mga students is kanang dili lang nato to sila I, dili lang nato to sila himuon nga pang discouraged sa atoa kanang himuon na hinuon nato nga kanang pan encourage sa atoa.” (IDI-01)

(The experiences we encounter as students, whether positive or challenging, should not just be about us. Instead of allowing them to discourage us, we can use them as opportunities to encourage ourselves and others.)

Celebrating Language Learning Progress with Positive Attitude. The third code of the second probed issue. According to the participants, celebrating language learning progress with positive attitude helps in maintaining motivation. They emphasize the importance of maintaining a positive mindset while acknowledging and appreciating the milestones achieved in the journey of language learning. Rather than solely focusing on fluency or perfection, this approach encourages individuals to recognize and celebrate their progress, regardless of how small it may seem.

Likewise, Fluentdream (pseudonym) finds motivation and satisfaction in witnessing advancements in her English language proficiency. She highlights the importance of celebrating small victories and progress with a positive attitude, particularly when she recognizes improvements in her English learning journey. This approach allows her to appreciate her growth, stay motivated, and maintain enthusiasm for further language development. She stated that:

“Those small wins and small victories of mine kay akoang siyang gina celebrate particularly pag makita jud nako sa akoang self nga nag improve ko when it comes to learning English.” (IDI-07)

(I celebrate those small wins and victories of mine, especially when I see myself improving in learning English.)

Furthermore, Knowquest (pseudonym) recognizes the significance of her minor improvements as catalysts for motivation. She emphasizes the importance of maintaining a positive attitude and celebrating her successes as ways to stay motivated in her language learning journey. She stated:

“I maintain a positive attitude and celebrate my success along the way keeps me motivated.” (FGD-03)

(Maintaining a positive attitude and celebrating my success along the way keeps me motivated.)

Similarly, Focusbright (pseudonym) acknowledges that recognizing individual progress fuels the drive to persevere in one’s endeavors. Every time she notices that she is doing something right and sees improvement, it motivates her even more to continue learning the language. This self-awareness and appreciation of her progress serve as powerful incentives to keep advancing in her English studies. She stated that:

“Mamotivate pud kay pag naay time ana nga sa akoang paminaw kay tama akoang gibuhay kay mura’g malipay ko mas ma motivate ko nga tama ni akoang gibuhay and uhm naa koy improvement ing ani.” (IDI-01)

(It also motivates me when there are moments when I realize that what I am doing is right, it’s like I feel happy, and it motivates me more because I know there’s improvement like this.)

Improving One’s Language Proficiency through Language Exposure and Setting Priorities. The third coping strategy of BEED students, which aligns with their motivational orientation toward learning English, seems to be influenced by similar responses from the participants. They emphasize that improving language proficiency can be achieved through increased exposure to the language and by setting clear priorities. Language exposure helps learners become familiar with the language’s nuances, vocabulary, and grammar structures in real-life contexts. Moreover, setting priorities involves identifying specific language learning goals and allocating time and resources accordingly. By prioritizing language learning activities and dedicating consistent effort to them, learners can effectively progress towards their proficiency goals.

Doing Time Management for Language Learning. The first code for the third probed issue. According to the participants, by dedicating study periods, engaging in regular language practice sessions, utilizing resources efficiently, and balancing language learning with other responsibilities the learners can maximize their learning potential, stay motivated, and make steady progress in mastering the language.

Likewise, Learnstar (pseudonym) shares that dedicating time to learning English is instrumental in sustaining her motivation for language acquisition. She recognizes that by investing time in English learning, the progress she achieves serves as a valuable long-term asset. She states:

“Imanage pud nimo ang imohang time nga naa jud kay time nga mainvest ani nga dapat karun mag learn diay ko og English syempre pag ma learn nimo dili naman jud na mawala sa imoha jud pag balik balikon nimo og kuaan dili naman jud na mawala so kibali didtoa nalang I kanang mag kuaan jud ka mag set jud ka ug time nga kanang dapat diria kini nga time dapat mag kuaan jud ko og English like ing ana gud.” (IDI- 03)

(I also manage my time, ensuring that I invest time in learning English. Because once you learn it, it is not something that you will lose, it stays with you. So, I allocate a specific time for English learning. For example, I set a time where I should be learning English.)

Moreover, Fluent (pseudonym) emphasizes that time management is crucial in achieving success in learning, particularly when mastering a new language like English. Prioritizing studying over less important activities ensures that you are dedicating enough time and energy to your goals. He remarked that:

“Importante jud nga imanage nimo imong oras kining dili importante nga gipangbuhat pangwalaon nato unahon najud ni ang pag study kay mao may mas importante.” (IDI-04)

(It is important to manage your time, prioritizing studying over less important activities. Studying should be given top priority.)

Furthermore, Fluentdream (pseudonym) highlights the importance of allocating dedicated time for English study, engaging in activities such as reading, practicing sentences, and watching English movies to enhance vocabulary and language skills. She also emphasizes that this structured approach helps her sustain motivation in learning the language. She expressed:

“Naga laan jud ko ana og time to learn the language like for example mag read ko og English books or magtan aw ba ko og movies kay in that way ma expand paman nako akoang vocabulary and by watching movies mura’g ma adapt pud nako how the characters speak so mura’g mas ma improve ko feel nako sa akoang pag learn sa English and that’s how I stayed motivated.” (IDI-07)

(I dedicate time to learning the language, like reading English books or watching movies. This helps expand my vocabulary, and by watching movies, I can adapt to how characters speak, which I feel improves my English learning and keeps me motivated.)

Additionally, Knowquest (pseudonym) showcased a persistent dedication to improving language proficiency. She described establishing a regular study schedule for learning English every day and fully committing herself to language learning during those dedicated times. She stated:

“I established a consistent study schedule by allocating specific time slot for each day for English learning activities in which helps me create a routine and ensures that I devote specific time for language practice.” (FGD- 03)

(I established a consistent study schedule by allocating specific time slots each day for English learning activities. This helps me create a routine and ensures that I devote specific time to language practice.)

Furthermore, Fluentpath (pseudonym) employs her time efficiently to study English. During the interview, she disclosed that she utilizes her free time to focus on studying English and expanding her vocabulary. This disciplined approach allows her to make consistent progress in her language learning, even with a busy schedule, ensuring that she maximizes every opportunity to improve her proficiency. She disclosed in the interview that:

“Whenever I have a free time, I studied English in order to adjust my habits or daily routines in order to effectively and efficiently learn English language and vocabulary.” (FGD-06)

(During my free time, I study English to adjust my habits and daily routines effectively and efficiently for learning the language and vocabulary.)

Finally, Studystrong (pseudonym) adjusts his daily routines and habits by implementing time management strategies and actively avoiding procrastination. This proactive approach helps him stay on track with his English studies and other responsibilities, ensuring that he makes steady progress without falling behind. By prioritizing tasks and minimizing distractions, he effectively manages his time to achieve his goals. According to his statement:

“Adjust my daily routines in my studying habits so I use time management to handle all the subjects that I had and all the materials that I had, time management and of course I avoid procrastination every time.” (FGD-07)

(I adjust my daily routines and study habits to manage my time effectively for all subjects and materials. I prioritize time management and avoid procrastination.)

Setting Goals for Language Learning. The second code of the third probed issue. As per the participants, establishing objectives for language acquisition proves beneficial in managing encountered challenges. They set feasible goals targeting particular areas for enhancing their English proficiency and adapt them if they realize they are unachievable within the designated timeframe.

Likewise, Languageheart (pseudonym) aims to improve both her English proficiency and personal motivation by setting practical objectives. By establishing achievable SMART goals, she effectively enhances her English skills while also sustaining her motivation to learn the language. According to her:

“By providing a goal or kanang goal nga kanang achievable gud siya ana mao na akoang gina set sa akoang mind para mas ma motivate sa pag sa pag gamit sa English.” (FGD-01)

(By setting achievable goals, that is what I set in my mind to motivate myself more in using English.)

Moreover, Knowquest (pseudonym) consistently enhances her English skills by setting SMART goals and breaking them down into smaller, manageable tasks. Additionally, she regularly evaluates her progress to determine if adjustments to her goals are necessary based on the challenges she faces. She expressed:

“So personally, I set SMART goals which is Specific Measurable Achievable Relevant and time bounded in which I will break them into smaller task regularly assess my progress adjust my goals needed base on the feedback and the challenges that I encountered.” (FGD-03)

(Personally, I set SMART goals – Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound. I break them into smaller tasks, regularly assess my progress, and adjust my goals based on feedback and challenges.)

Furthermore, Fluentpath (pseudonym) employs a strategy of establishing sequential objectives and adjusting them if they become unachievable within the allocated timeframe. Personally, setting step-by-step goals, he adapts them if they cannot be accomplished within a day. He mentioned:

“So, I personally set goals by making step by step on what will I achieve or kanang iadjust nako akoang goals kung pag dili nako siya ma achieve within this day.” (FGD-06)

(I set goals by outlining step-by-step what I want to achieve and adjust them if I can not achieve them within a day.)

Exposing Oneself to the Language Use. Is the third code for the third probed issue. Based on the participants' feedback from the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, another tactic they employ is immersing themselves in the English language. This involves consistently practicing their speaking skills to enhance their proficiency in the language. This includes practicing speaking, listening, reading, and writing in English regularly. By immersing oneself in English-language environments, individuals can become more comfortable and proficient in using the language effectively.

Leximind (pseudonym) emphasizes that before every classroom demonstration, she engages in advanced practice to improve her pronunciation and fluency. She rehearses in front of a mirror, using the language to refine her speaking skills and build confidence. This method allows her to identify and correct any issues with her delivery, helping her perform more effectively in the classroom. She

states:

“Every naa koy demo naga tan aw naga face jud ko sa kanang mirror namo sa balay naga you know naga storya storya ko didtoa using English gina check nako og tama ba akoang pag pronounce, kung tama ba ang kaning paglitok nako ato tapos okay lang ba ang akoang kanang voice fluent ba ko paminawon.” (IDI-05)

(Whenever I have a demo, I practice speaking in front of the mirror at home using English. I check if my pronunciation is correct, if my intonation is right, and if my voice sounds fluent.)

Moreover, Fluentdream (pseudonym) implements a strategy of active practice and dedicated effort to improve her English language skills. She enhances her proficiency by consistently practicing speaking in English, which also helps her maintain motivation in her language learning journey. She shared in the interview that:

“Every naa koy demo naga tan aw naga face jud ko sa kanang mirror namo sa balay naga you know naga storya storya ko didtoa using English gina check nako og tama ba akoang pag pronounce, kung tama ba ang kaning paglitok nako ato tapos okay lang ba ang akoang kanang voice fluent ba ko paminawon.” (IDI-07)

(Whenever I have a demo, I practice speaking in front of the mirror at home using English. I check if my pronunciation is correct, if my intonation is right, and if my voice sounds fluent.)

Furthermore, Wordchaser (pseudonym) ensures she is prepared for presentations, reports, and other activities by continuously engaging in self-directed practice to refine her pronunciation every time she speaks English. Like other respondents, she also commits to advanced practice to bolster her confidence in expressing ideas through spoken English. She mentioned during the interview that:

“Gina practice lang nako akoang kaugalingon daan kung unsa ang proper nga pronunciation ani nga word para nga kung naa nako sa actual diko maulawan. So, kung naa koy mga, diman jud malikayan no nga naa koy mga reports and any nga mga activities so kuaan kining gina prepare nako akoang sarili daan para nga ma okay ang akoang presentation.” (IDI-02)

(I practice pronouncing words properly in advance so that I will not feel embarrassed when I am actually speaking and whenever I have reports or activities, I prepare myself in advance to ensure that my presentation goes well.)

Employing Collaborative Learning and Technological Support. Is the last essential theme for the coping mechanism of BEED students with regards to the challenges on motivational orientation on learning English. Based on the collective input from the participants regarding the second research question, it was found that another coping mechanism of BEED students is to seek support from their peers, fostering collaborative learning among students. Additionally, they also utilized technology to look up unfamiliar words. Through this strategy, students are able to improve their English proficiency and sustain their motivation to learn the language.

Value Support and Feedback provided by others. Is the first code for the fourth probed issue. During the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, participants conveyed that valuing the support and feedback received from others aids in enhancing their English proficiency. By attentively considering the suggestions provided, participants become aware of areas they need to improve to achieve mastery in the English language.

Similarly, Wordchaser (pseudonym) actively seeks assistance and clarification from her friends and housemates whenever she encounters challenges in the English language. She specifically requests their input and clarification, particularly regarding the correct pronunciation of words. She mentioned that:

“So nagapangayo ko ug support everytime nga naa koy mga kalibgan about sa English sa akoang mga friends, sa akoang mga kauban diria sa boarding house, everytime nga naa koy kalibgan mangayo ko sa ilaha ug mga idea, kung unsaon nila pagsabot kung unsaon ni siya for example sa mga pronunciation mag ask ko sa ilaha kung unsa ang pronunciation ani nga word.” (IDI-02)

(I seek support from my friends and housemates whenever I have doubts about English. I ask for their ideas and clarification, especially on pronunciation, by requesting them to provide the correct pronunciation of certain words.)

Additionally, Learnstar (pseudonym) utilizes a strategy of seeking assistance from a friend to correct errors in English grammar, sentence structure, and usage. By asking for guidance on constructing sentences properly or correcting grammar, she effectively addresses the challenges encountered in her English language journey. In her interview, she stated that:

“Sa mga friends sad nimo kay kibali ingnan ka nga dili man ing ana dai, usahay naa say instances nga mangayo ko og tabang nga unsa may kuaan ani dai kanang unsay tawag ana unsa man juy dapat nga kanang, unsay may tama diria kani nga sentence, unsa ang tama nga structure ani dapat niya kung namali na ba siya’g grammar.” (IDI-03)

(With friends, you can ask them directly for help, saying something like, ‘I am not sure about this,’ and sometimes I ask for assistance on how to properly structure sentences or correct grammar mistakes.)

Furthermore, Fluentdream (pseudonym) consistently seeks feedback from a proficient English-speaking friend to enhance her English speaking and writing skills. She relies on her friend’s assistance to identify any errors in her work. This strategy allows her to monitor her progress in English proficiency, which further motivates her to continue learning the language. She highlighted in the interview

that:

“So I have a friend and slash classmate no nga hawd jud siya mag English speaking and writing so tapos sa amoang isa ka subject kay naa man miy mga literary criticism nga ginabuhat ba so uhm akoang tong gina pa check sa iyaha if tama and okay lang ba akoang pagbuhat, akoang writing kung tama ba and kung nindot ba and makita pud jud nako akoang progress kay katong mga na collect nako nga words kay at some point magamit nako siya through writing and through speaking pud for example kanang naa me mga oral recitation so magamit na nako and makita na nako akoang progress sa paglearn og English.” (IDI-07)

(I have a friend who is really good at English speaking and writing. In one of our subjects where we do literary criticism, I ask them to check my work to ensure correctness and quality. This helps me track my progress, as I collect new words that I can eventually use in writing and speaking, such as during oral recitations.)

Seeking Assistance on Language Learning through Technology. Is the second code for the fourth probed issue. According to the participants' feedback from the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, integrating technology into language learning can significantly improve English proficiency. By leveraging technology, learners can boost their efficiency, effectiveness, and motivation, accessing valuable support and resources tailored to their needs. Incorporating digital tools and resources into language learning enables learners to enhance their skills more dynamically and conveniently, contributing to a more engaging and productive language learning journey.

Similarly, Learnstar (pseudonym) expressed that utilizing technology to seek help when encountering difficulties in learning the English language is convenient for her. By accessing various online channels discussing English-related topics, she finds it easy to comprehend complex concepts in English. She mentioned during the interview that:

“Karun kay diba technology advanced naman kaayo ta so kadalasan kay dili na kaayo ta mag open up sa ubang tao personally nga ay unsaon mani pag kuaan ani unsa may dagan aning kini nga kuaan kining unsay tawag ana basta kining related sa English ba diba kadalasan sa mag kuaan nalang man ta mga social media or sa YouTube kay daghan man pud gud siya mga channel ba nga naga naga tudlo og kining English mga ing ana so kibalì diraa nalang ka diraa nalang ka naga kuaan usahay.” (IDI-03)

(Nowadays, with advanced technology, we often turn to social media or YouTube for learning English-related topics. There are many channels that teach English, so it's more convenient to seek help there.)

Moreover, Wordseeker (pseudonym) actively leveraged technology, particularly in the process of discovering unfamiliar words, throughout his journey of English language acquisition. By utilizing digital resources such as online dictionaries and language learning apps, he efficiently addressed vocabulary gaps and expanded his linguistic knowledge. He affirmed in the interview that:

“I always seek help in technologies I, I search those words that I didn't understand so that technology can help me in distinguishing those words and also to keep me motivated in learning English vocabulary.” (FGD-05)

(I rely on technology to help me understand unfamiliar words and to stay motivated in learning English vocabulary.)

Furthermore, Fluentpath (pseudonym) emphasizes the integration of technology as the primary approach to overcome challenges in learning English. He relies on technology as a support system whenever he encounters difficulties, leveraging digital tools and resources to address language learning obstacles effectively. He conveyed that:

“So, when I faced difficulties in learning English that strategies that I will be going to use is the technology, we all know naman na nata sa technology karun 21st century so I use technology to my daily basis, do research all the difficulties that I had.” (FGD-06)

(When facing difficulties in learning English, I turn to technology. In this digital age, technology is readily available, so I use it daily to research and overcome challenges.)

Insights Shared by BEED Students with Regards to the Motivational Orientation on Learning English

Table 5 displays the scrutinized and synthesized notions in the insights of BEED students with regards to their motivational orientation on learning the English language. As a result of the thematic analysis, 4 essential themes emerged namely: recognizing that language proficiency is essential in personal and professional growth, giving importance to the role of motivation on language proficiency, importance of having a supportive environment for feedback and self-expression, and acknowledging the role of English in global context.

Importance of Maintaining Motivation for English Language Proficiency amidst Challenges. The primary recurring idea emerging from both the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions is that participants acknowledge the crucial role of language proficiency in both personal and academic advancement. They highlight the importance of maintaining motivation in learning English through self-encouragement and a resilient mindset. Resilience and Motivation on Learning English. The first code of the first probe issue. According to the participants, resilience and motivation are pivotal factors in the language learning process. They deem resilience and motivation crucial because when faced with obstacles like language barriers, struggles with grammar comprehension, or fear of errors, having resilience empowers them to overcome these challenges.

Table 5. Insights Shared by BEED Students with Regards to the Motivational Orientation on Learning

ISSUES PROBED	CORE IDEAS	CATEGORIES/ CODES	ESSENTIAL THEMES	THEORETICAL SUPPORT
<p>Maintaining Motivation Under-scores the Importance of Self-Encouragement and a Resilient mindset.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emphasizing the importance of self-encouragement and the mindset that challenges should not hinder the learning journey Challenges can serve as inspiration or stepping stones towards personal growth Recognizing the significance of staying motivated. 	<p>Resilience and Motivation on Learning English</p>	<p>Importance of Maintaining Motivation for English Language Proficiency amidst Challenges</p>	<p>Goal-Setting Theory</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Belief in the learnability of everything hinges on maintaining a positive mindset and trusting in one's capabilities Encouraging persistence amidst adversity or moments of disinterest Emphasizing the importance of concentration and seriousness in learning, particularly when tackling challenging subjects such as English 	<p>Overcoming Challenges in English Language Learning through Perseverance</p>		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acknowledging the initial challenges of learning English, yet realizing that the journey can be fulfilling Cultivating a positive attitude, fostering self-assurance, and depending on one's own capabilities while also underscoring the value of assisting fellow students in their learning journey Highlighting the personal development and benefits derived from 	<p>Emphasizing Self Fulfillment and Growth in English Language Proficiency</p>		

	<p>persisting through the difficulties inherent in learning English</p>			
<p>Cultivating eagerness to master English which Serves as a buffer against Fatigue and Setbacks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The significance of motivation in English learning and its correlation with the development of fundamental communication skills • Linking the correlation between the motivation to learn English and the improvement of communication skills • The significance lies in educators' ability to effectively convey information coupled with the importance of practicing English • Proficiency in English can foster better communication skills, thereby enhancing one's capacity to socialize effectively • English proficiency can greatly facilitate effective communication to both students and colleagues • The significance of motivation in learning English is paramount for aspiring educators 	<p>Relevance of Motivation in Mastering English Language and Communication Skills</p>	<p>Recognizing that Language Proficiency is Essential in Personal and Professional Growth</p>	<p>Expectancy-Value Theory</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The proficiency in English among teachers is crucial as they are the main conduits of information and communication • English proficiency holds significant weight for educators within the educational sphere • Underlining the fact that educators cannot proficiently teach a language they 	<p>Significance of English Proficiency towards Teaching Effectiveness</p>		

	<p>themselves do not comprehend</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The substantial impact of motivation on English learning, underlining that insufficient motivation results in a diminished enthusiasm for language study • The necessity of sustaining motivation in language learning pursuits • Motivation serves as a buffer against fatigue and discouragement during learning 	<p>Motivation Plays Crucial Role on English Language Learning</p>		
<p>Embracing criticisms for English Skill Enhancement</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognizing the value of utilizing criticism as a driving force to enhance English skills, emphasizing the importance of maintaining a mindset centered on continual learning and development despite encountering criticism • Embracing the importance of receiving feedback and corrections particularly from educators or individuals with higher proficiency in English, as a means to ignite motivation and pursue ongoing enhancements in English proficiency • Acknowledging the significance of treating feedback and challenges from instructors or mentors with seriousness, perceiving them as avenues for personal advancement 	<p>Accepting Criticisms and Feedbacks for English Language Growth</p>	<p>Importance of Having a Supportive Environment for Feedback and Self-Expression</p>	<p>Sociocultural Theory</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encouraging individuals to speak up without hesitation, even if 	<p>Encourage Self-Expression Using English Language</p>		

	<p>they make mistakes, particularly when expressing their own ideas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advising individuals not to be afraid to express themselves and utilize English as their primary language 			
The Impact of Motivation to Language Learning Attainment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aspiring to teach abroad, the individual feels compelled to study English diligently, aiming to communicate effectively upon arrival and seamlessly adapt to the language and culture of the destination • Recognizing the importance of English as a universal language. • Mastering English will empower Speakers to provide top-notch education to students from various international backgrounds 	Motivation to Teach Internationally Plays a Role in English Language Proficiency	Acknowledging the Role of English Proficiency in Global Context	Motivation Theory
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The impact of globalization under-scores the imperative idea to learn English • Learning English is crucial as it functions as the universal language which essential for effective communication • Obtaining essential teaching proficiency in English offers chances to teach in other countries 	Recognizing English Proficiency as Fundamental Skill in Global Landscape		

“Despite sa mga challenges no is na learn nako nga na motivate gihapon ko nga mag learn ra gihapon og more in English. So gina encourage nimo imohang sarili nga despite sa mga challenges nga akoang na encounter akoang gina tatak sa akoang hunahuna nga kanang dili na siya maka hinder nga para stop nako akoang paglearning.” (IDI-02)

(Despite the challenges I encountered, I still find myself motivated to continue learning more in English. I encourage myself that despite these challenges, they won’t hinder my learning journey.)

Moreover, Learnstar (pseudonym) holds the belief that challenges can serve as sources of inspiration or steppingstones for personal growth in learning English. This perspective allows her to embrace difficulties as opportunities for development, using them to

strengthen her language skills and boost her confidence. As she expressed in interview:

“Daghan jud kaayo og mga challenges pero kato nga mga challenges himuon to nimo siya nga inspiration ba or stepping stone nga bisag lisod siya pero afterwards ako ra gihapon ang maka benefit.” (IDI-03)

(There are indeed many challenges, but you can turn those challenges into inspiration or stepping stones. Even though they may be difficult, in the end, I will be the one who benefits.)

Furthermore, Fluentdream (pseudonym) stressed the importance of maintaining motivation in learning English, emphasizing that without it, navigating the language’s complexities can become daunting, particularly when facing challenges. She believes that staying motivated is crucial for overcoming obstacles and continuing to make progress in language learning. She articulated that:

“Regardless sa akoang mga challenges nga na encounter sa pag learn nako og English I learned that staying motivated sa pag learn sa language kay have a significant impact, kay without your motivation on learning something or maskin unsa paman na dili jud ka makatuon.” (IDI-07)

(Regardless of the challenges I faced in learning English, I have learned that staying motivated in language learning has a significant impact. Without motivation, it is hard to learn anything.)

Overcoming Challenges in Language Learning through Perseverance. The second code for the first probed issue. Based on their interview responses, it's evident that they have the ability to surmount obstacles in language learning by adopting a resilient mindset. Instead of allowing challenges to deter them, they choose to see them as chances for personal development and advancement. This approach suggests a determination to persist and find value in the learning process, ultimately leading to greater progress and success in mastering the language.

Readspark (pseudonym) conveyed the belief that with a positive mindset and self-belief, she can learn anything, even when facing challenges. This optimistic outlook empowers her to tackle difficulties head-on, confident that she can overcome obstacles and achieve her learning goals. She emphasized that:

“I can say is that everything is can be learn basta kay always positive lang ta nga kaya nato dili lang ta mawad an ug salig sa atoang kaugalingon because nothing is difficult if you are eager to learn.” (FGD-04)

(I can say that everything can be learned as long as we remain positive and believe in ourselves because nothing is difficult if you are eager to learn.)

Readspark (pseudonym) conveyed the belief that with a positive mindset and self-belief, she can learn anything, even when facing challenges. She sees these qualities as essential for overcoming obstacles and achieving success in learning English and other endeavors. In her interview, she articulated:

“I can say is that everything is can be learn basta kay always positive lang ta nga kaya nato dili lang ta mawad an ug salig sa atoang kaugalingon because nothing is difficult if you are eager to learn.” (FGD-04)

(I can say that everything can be learned as long as we remain positive and believe in ourselves because nothing is difficult if you are eager to learn.)

Additionally, Learnstar (pseudonym) consistently relies on encouragement and persistence whenever she encounters adversity or loses interest in learning English. These strategies help her stay focused and motivated, allowing her to overcome challenges and maintain her commitment to improving her language skills. In her interview, she noted:

“So kanang ing ana kanang padayun lang jud, although lisud siya karun ma unmotivated ka pero hunahunaon lang jud nimo nga at the end of the day naa rajud na sa imo naa rajud na sa imo kanang sa imoha ra japun na ang kanang balik ana ba kibali ikaw ra gihapon ang maka benefit so bisan lisud padayun lang jud. (IDI-03)

(So, just keep going, even if it is hard right now and you feel unmotivated. Always remember that at the end of the day, it is all up to you. You are the one who will benefit from it. So, even if it is difficult, just keep going.)

Furthermore, Fluent (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of concentration and seriousness in learning, especially when tackling challenging subjects like English. She believes that maintaining focus and a dedicated attitude are crucial for effectively overcoming difficulties and making significant progress in language learning. In the interview, he stated that:

“Dapat nga kuaan mag focus jud kanang dili nimo kuaan ba easy easyhan ang kuaan man jud lisud man jud ni siya nga subject kay kinahanglan man nimo sabton, kinahanglan jud nimo i kuaan ang mga words kailangan nimo i understanding, kailangan jud i understand jud nimo og tarong ba maoy kuaan sa English lisud jud siya sabton.” (IDI-04)

(You should focus and not take it lightly. Learning English is not easy because you need to understand and grasp the words properly. You need to comprehend and understand them correctly because if you do not, it will be difficult to answer.)

Emphasizing Self-Fulfillment and Growth in English Language Proficiency. The third code of the first probed issue, as indicated by the participants' responses during the interview, suggests that language learning encompasses more than just acquiring language skills. It emphasizes the importance of prioritizing personal fulfillment and growth despite experiencing challenges throughout the learning process. This perspective implies that language learning goes beyond achieving a specific proficiency level, it also involves personal enrichment and advancement.

Learnstar (pseudonym) highlights the importance of acknowledging the challenges inherent in learning English while also emphasizing the potential for fulfillment in the journey. She believes that recognizing and confronting difficulties is crucial, but the rewards and personal growth gained from overcoming these challenges can be deeply satisfying and motivating. In her interview, she revealed:

“Pag mag learn ka og English lisud man jud no so dapat imoha lang jung ibutang iinstill sa imohang mindset nga lisud siya pero afterwards satisfying man pud ang kanang kuaan, satisfying man pud ang iyahang result.” (IDI-03)

(When learning English, it can indeed be challenging, but you should instill in your mindset that although it is difficult, the satisfaction and results afterward make it worthwhile.)

Moreover, Wordchaser (pseudonym) emphasizes that facing challenges and difficulties in learning English is inevitable, but maintaining a positive outlook is essential. By encouraging herself and believing in her abilities significantly boost her self-confidence. She indicated in the interview that:

“Maka experience ta og mga challenges and difficulties in learning English so dapat ime itatak nimo sa imohang sarili nga mura’g iencourage nimo imohang kaugalingon or be positive enough para nga mo think ka og positive nga kaya nimo ni dapat e improve nimo imohang self confidence which is makatabang pud siya sa other students, importante man gud nga naa sa atoang hunahuna nga kining nagsalig ta sa atoang kaugalingon ba nga kaya nato ni ana.” (IDI-02)

(We will encounter challenges and difficulties in learning English, so you should encourage yourself or maintain a positive outlook. Think positively that you can improve your self-confidence, which can also help other students. It is important to have the mindset that we trust ourselves and believe that we can do it.)

Furthermore, Learnstar (pseudonym) underscores that instead of focusing solely on the difficulties, it’s important for one to recognize that despite the challenges, the outcome is ultimately in their hands. While learning English may be hard, the effort invested will directly benefit the individual in the long run. She mentioned during the interview that:

“Dili lang jud nimo hunahunaon nga lisod pero imohang hunahunaon nga although lisud siya pero after all naa rajud na sa imoha, ikaw rajuy maka benefit ana, naa rajud sa imohang kuaan. (IDI-03)

(Do not just think about the difficulty, but instead, think that although it is hard, it is ultimately up to you. You are the one who will benefit from it. It is all in your hands.)

Recognizing that Language Proficiency is Essential in Personal and Professional Growth. The second recurring idea arise from the insights of BEED students with regards to the motivational orientation on learning

English. The participants in both the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions consistently recognize the crucial role of motivation in their journey toward English language proficiency. They understand that cultivating a strong eagerness to learn and improve their English skills is essential. This motivation serves as a protective factor, helping them to overcome challenges such as fatigue or setbacks that may arise during the learning process. In essence, maintaining high levels of motivation acts as a driving force that keeps them engaged and determined to succeed in mastering the English language.

Relevance of Motivation in Mastering English Language and Communication. The first code of the second probed issue. Based on the responses of the participants during the interview, it is clear that they emphasized the importance of motivation in mastering the English language and communication skills. They recognize that staying motivated plays a significant role in their ability to learn and effectively use English in various contexts. This underscores the understanding that without sufficient motivation, achieving proficiency in English can be challenging. Therefore, their emphasis on motivation highlights its critical role as a driving force behind successful language acquisition and communication.

Similarly, Readspark (pseudonym) notices the significance of motivation in English learning and its correlation with the development of fundamental communication skills. She observes that a strong sense of motivation not only drives progress in language acquisition but also enhances essential communication abilities, facilitating more effective and confident interactions. She affirmed in the interview that:

“I’m learning myself that our motivation is important in learning different things especially in learning English and I always found essential ang communication skills in order to succeed in education field kung kanang duha mag coincide so you have your bigger chance to achieve your dreams to be ay in the future.” (FGD-04)

(I am learning that motivation is crucial in learning various things, especially English, and I find communication skills essential for success in the education field. When these two coincide, you have a greater chance of achieving your dreams in the future.)

Moreover, Fluentdream (pseudonym) perceives that there is a clear connection between one's motivation to learn English and the development of essential communication skills, which are crucial for success in education. Proficiency in English not only enhances communication abilities but also improves the effectiveness of interactions with students in the future. She revealed during the interview that:

"I see a direct link between my motivation to learn English and my essential skills for success in education kay if hawd naka mo speak og English ma enhance man imihang communication skills so in that way mas ma effective nga, effective imohang interaction sa imohang students in the future." (IDI-07)

(I see a direct link between my motivation to learn English and my essential communication skills for success in education. If you are proficient in English, it enhances your communication skills, making your interaction with students more effective in the future.)

In addition, Focusbright (pseudonym) expresses that, as a future educator, it is crucial to have the ability to effectively convey information, which underscores the importance of practicing English. Mastery of the language is essential for clear and impactful communication, vital for successful teaching and engaging with students. She expressed during the interview that:

"As a teacher should have is that the ability to disseminate information very well so i connection in learning, in connection with motivation in learning English of course if you are teacher in the making it is effective for you to disseminate information but also consider your ano also consider to practice English beause some students might misinterpret, might misinterpret some information you disseminate." (IDI-01)

(As a teacher, it is important to disseminate information effectively, which connects with the motivation to learn English. If you are unable to communicate well in English, students might misinterpret the information you provide.)

Furthermore, Learnstar (pseudonym) believes that proficiency in English can foster better communication skills, thereby enhancing one's capability to socialize effectively. Mastering the language not only improves the ability to interact with others but also facilitates more meaningful and productive social engagements. In her interview, she mentioned:

"Kung hawd ka og English diba ang imohang communication skills kay ma improve pud na imohang kanang basta the way you kanang unsa na kanang the way ka makig socialize ka." (IDI-03)

(If you are proficient in English, your communication skills and the way you socialize can also improve.)

Similarly, Fluentpath (pseudonym) expressed that to succeed in the field of education, acquiring essential skills like communication is crucial. As a teacher, effective communication is key to engaging and connecting with students. Without strong communication skills, it becomes difficult to convey ideas, provide instructions, and foster a supportive learning environment. She revealed during the interview that:

"Maka help jud siya sa imoha in the future kung unsaon nimo siya pag communicate sa imohang students sa imohang uhm ka workmate and especially sa imohang mga students kung unsaon nimo sila paghandle, kabalo ka kung unsaon nimo lag communicate with your students." (FGD-06)

(To succeed in the field of education, there are skills we need to acquire, such as communication skills. As a teacher, effective communication is crucial because if you cannot communicate well, you will not be able to effectively engage with your students. So, it is important for us to focus on learning and improving these skills, including English proficiency.)

Moreover, Learnswell (pseudonym) expresses that having motivation in learning English is essential because it is closely tied to developing strong communication skills, which are crucial for educators in understanding and meeting the diverse needs of students. This motivation is necessary to achieve success in the future field of education. In her interview, she stated that:

"For me it is very important to have a motivation in learning English and also it can link with my skills because as a future educator we need to have a strong communication skills in order to communicate and to comprehend and in order to attain the diverse need of our students so it should be have motivation in order to achieve those things in the future field." (IDI-06)

(For me, having motivation in learning English is essential because it is linked to developing strong communication skills, which are crucial for educators to understand and meet the diverse needs of students. Having motivation is necessary to achieve these goals in the future field.)

Significance of English Proficiency towards Teaching Effectiveness. The second code of the second probed issue. Based on the responses of the participants during the interview, it is evident that they highlighted the importance of English proficiency for enhancing teaching effectiveness. This implies that they believe being proficient in English positively impacts their ability to teach effectively which can lead to better understanding and retention of the material being taught.

Focusbright (pseudonym) expresses the view that proficiency in English is crucial for teachers, as they serve as the primary channels of information and communication. Effective communication in English is essential for delivering instruction clearly and engagingly, ensuring that students receive accurate and comprehensive knowledge. She mentions that:

“It is very important to a teacher to become smart or excellent in speaking English because you are the source of information, you are the one who disseminate information so as much as possible you need to be careful and mao to need nimo nga mag very careful kay kung unsa na imohang mga gipang storya dihaa i absorb man gud na sa imohang students.” (IDI-01)

(It is very important for a teacher to be smart or excellent in speaking English because they are the source of information and they disseminate it to their students. Therefore, they need to be very careful about what they convey because their students absorb everything they say.)

Moreover, Wordchaser (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of English proficiency for educators within the educational sphere. She believes that by demonstrating proficiency in English to her students, she can inspire them to engage more actively in learning the language. She stated that:

“Importante siya in the field of education kay soon if naa nako sa field as teacher so magamit nako to siya magamit nako ang kining mastery in speaking English and at the same time mura’g maka hatag pud siya ug inspiration sa other students just like for example kanang naa naka sa field tapos hawd ka mo tudlo og English tapos ma motivate oud ang mga bata nga mo learn pa og more sa English.” (IDI-02)

(It is crucial in the field of education because soon, when I am in the field as a teacher, I will be able to use my mastery of speaking English to inspire other students. For example, if students see a teacher who is proficient in English, it can motivate them to learn more.)

Furthermore, Leximind (pseudonym) underlines the facts that It is crucial for educators to have a strong grasp of English because without proper knowledge and teaching skills in the language, they will be unable to effectively educate their students. Mastery of English is essential not only for personal proficiency but also for ensuring that students receive a high-quality education. She stated that:

“As a BEED student kanang English part naman jud na siya sa atoa nga dapat pud nato iitudlo sa mga bata so kung kita nga educators wala ta wala kabalo or waka ta nagtuon or walabta nag prepare og di nato wala ta kabalo anang English nga language unsaon nato pagtudlo sa atoa nga mga students so we cannot teach if we don’t know.” (IDI-05)

(As a BEED student, English is an essential part of our education that we need to teach to children. As educators, if we do not know or have not learned how to teach English properly, we will not be able to effectively educate our students.)

Motivation Plays a Crucial Role on English Language Learning. The third code of the second probed issue. Participants consistently emphasized the importance of motivation in the process of learning the English language. This implies that they recognize motivation as a key factor that significantly influences their ability to learn English effectively. When learners are motivated, they are more likely to engage actively in language learning activities, persist through challenges, and seek out opportunities to improve their skills.

Readspark (pseudonym) emphasizes the substantial impact of motivation on English learning, noting that insufficient motivation can lead to diminished enthusiasm for language acquisition. She believes that maintaining strong motivation is key to sustaining interest and making consistent progress in learning the language. She revealed during the interview that:

“Naa juy impact atoaang motivation on learning English if you are not motivated enough in learning it wala jud kay gana to study more in English, so our motivation have a great contribution to us to be eager to learn more in English.” (FGD-04)

(Our motivation greatly impacts our learning of English. If we lack motivation, we will not have the drive to study English more. Therefore, motivation plays a crucial role in fueling our eagerness to learn more in English.)

Moreover, Wordseeker (pseudonym) expressed the importance of having motivation when studying or learning English, as it increases eagerness and commitment to the process. Motivation drives individuals to engage more deeply with the material, overcome challenges, and stay focused on their goals, making the learning experience more effective and rewarding. She shared in the interview that:

“So the key lessons that I have learned is maayo jud nga naa tay motivation regarding mag study ta or mag learn English language kay mao na mas makapa eager sa atoa ug tuon.” (FGD-05)

(One key lesson I have learned is the importance of having motivation when studying or learning the English language because it makes us more eager to learn.)

Furthermore, according to Learnstar (pseudonym), when motivated, individuals are less likely to become tired, discouraged, or lose interest. Motivation fuels persistence and enthusiasm, helping to overcome obstacles and maintain focus on learning goals. It acts as a driving force that sustains energy and commitment throughout the educational journey. She stated that:

“Kung motivated ta dili ta dali kapoyon dili ka kuaan dili ka dali ma wala nga ay di nako ganahan.” (IDI-03)

(When we are motivated, we will not easily get tired, discouraged, or lose interest.)

Importance of Having a Supportive Environment for Feedback and Self-Expression. The third key theme emerging from BEED

students' perspectives on motivation in learning English highlights the importance of a supportive learning atmosphere. Both in-depth interviews and focus group discussions revealed that participants stressed the value of an environment that promotes feedback and facilitates self-expression. Within this setting, individuals can freely share their thoughts and ideas without worrying about criticism. Additionally, receiving constructive feedback enables learners to pinpoint areas needing improvement and gain guidance on enhancing language skills. This continuous feedback loop contributes to ongoing learning and personal development.

Accepting Criticism and Feedbacks for English Language Growth. The first code of the third probed issue. Participants have come to understand that feedback, even if critical, plays a valuable role in their language development. By being open to feedback, they can identify areas where they need improvement and take necessary steps to address them. Accepting criticism also demonstrates a willingness to learn and grow, which is essential for language proficiency.

Similarly, Learnstar (pseudonym) articulates the significance of acknowledging the value of criticism as a driving force to improve English skills. She underscores the importance of maintaining a mindset focused on continual learning and development, even in the face of criticism. She stated that:

“Kung usahay nag storya ka og English niya na criticize ka himuon to nimo siyang motivation nga sa sunod dapat dili lang diay ko didto dapat kutob, dapat kining mas maningkamot pa diay ko kay kung hawd kay ka mo storya og English daghan man pud kaayo siya og opportunities nga maghulat sa imoha so dapat ing ato lang jud dapat ang mindset nga kung ma criticize ka di kuaan dapat mao to ang wake up call sa imoha nga mas mag learn jud ka og English kay after all dili mana pasabot nga kung mag English ka hawd najud kaayo ing ana pero ang ang ending man gud ana kay ikaw raman gihapon ang maka benefit so mura’g ing ana lang jud siya.” (IDI – 03)

(Sometimes, when you speak English and get criticized, you should take it as motivation. Instead of feeling discouraged, you should see it as an opportunity to improve. Criticism should be a wake-up call to learn English better because being criticized does not mean you are not good at English. In the end, you are the one who will benefit. It is just like that.)

Moreover, Leximind (pseudonym) also highlights that it is important to be open to feedback, especially from teachers or those more proficient in English. Accepting their corrections and feedback should be seen as motivation to work harder and improve your English skills. Embracing constructive criticism helps identify areas for growth and drives you to make meaningful progress in your learning journey. As she mentioned in the interview that:

“Pag icorrect ka dapat open ka sa mga kanang feedbacks or corrections especially sa imohang mga teachers or kanang mga mas labaw sa imoha nga mas kabalo og English so dapat open lang ka dapat mo accept ka og mga corrections nila no mga feedback tapos gamiton to nimo nga motivation para mas mag pursigi nga mag learn og English.” (IDI-05)

(When you are corrected, you should be open to feedback, especially from your teachers or those who are more proficient in English. Accept their corrections and feedback as motivation to strive harder to learn English.)

Furthermore, according to Knowquest (pseudonym), embracing feedback and the challenges presented by teachers or tutors is crucial for personal and academic growth. By viewing these as opportunities for improvement, individuals can refine their English skills and enhance their overall learning experience. She stated that:

“Take feedbacks and the challenges that was being thrown by your teacher or your own tutor lightly and make a better in which it makes yourself a better individual who have a better English skills.” (FGD-03)

(Embrace feedback and the challenges presented by your teachers or tutors, and use them to improve yourself and your English skills.)

Encourage Self-Expression Using English Language. The second code of the third probed issue. Participants have come to understand that to enhance their proficiency in using the English language, they must encourage self-expression using the language. By this, they are likely to become more comfortable and confident in using the language. This active engagement facilitates language acquisition and mastery as it provides opportunities to practice and apply language skills in real-life contexts.

Studyglow (pseudonym) emphasizes that individuals should not hesitate to speak up, especially when expressing their own ideas using English, even if they make mistakes. She encourages embracing opportunities to communicate, as making mistakes is a natural part of the learning process and crucial for improvement. She stated that:

“Don’t hesitate to storya bisan pa og mali na siya kay own idea man ang gina unsa, especially kung own idea ang ginapangayo so ing ana.” (FGD-02)

(Feel free to speak up, even if you make mistakes, because it is your own ideas that matter, especially when you’re asked for your own input. That’s how it is.)

Similarly, Fluentpath (pseudonym) advises individuals not to be afraid to express themselves and to use English as their primary language. She encourages embracing the language fully, as doing so can enhance their communication skills and build confidence in using English. He highlighted in the interview that:

“Don’t be afraid to show yourself and use English as a medium of language in a daily basis.” (FGD-06)

(Do not hesitate to express yourself and use English in your daily conversations.)

Acknowledging the Role of English Proficiency in Global Context. The last key theme emerging from BEED students' insights on motivation in learning English acknowledge the role of English proficiency in global context. Both in-depth interviews and focus group discussions highlighted that the participants placed significant emphasis on the relevance of English proficiency for global communication and interaction. They acknowledge that English proficiency opens up opportunities for international collaboration, employment, and cultural exchange.

Motivation to Teach Internationally Plays a Role in English Language Proficiency. The first code of the fourth probed issue. The participants' feedback from both the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions suggests that they are motivated to improve their English proficiency in order to pursue teaching opportunities internationally. Their desire to enhance their English skills is likely fueled by the prospect of teaching in countries where English is the primary language or commonly used for instruction. They understand the importance of having strong English proficiency for effective communication with students, colleagues, and parents from various linguistic and cultural backgrounds.

Leximind (pseudonym) articulates that her aspiration to teach abroad serves as the driving force behind her diligent study of English. This motivation arises from the necessity to communicate effectively with individuals who speak the language, fueling her commitment to mastering English and achieving her professional goals. She stated that:

“Gusto ko magtudlo sa laing nasod so tungod ato mas namotivate ko nga magtuon jud og English para pag abot nako didto is maka communicate ko sa ilaha dayun and then maka adjust ko sa mga ilahang kumbaga sa ilahang language kung in case man English language pud ang ilahang ginagamit didtoa mas dali ko maka adjust maka communicate sa ilaha so mao to kanang pagtudlo didtoa mas naka motvate sa akoa nga mas magtuon karun og English.” (IDI-05)

(I want to teach in another country, so because of that, I am more motivated to really study English. When I get there, I will be able to communicate with them right away, and if they also use English, it will be easier for me to adjust and communicate with them. So, teaching there motivates me to study English more now.)

Moreover, Fluentdream (pseudonym) conveyed that mastering English would facilitate her ability to teach in another country. With English proficiency, she would be adept at communicating effectively with others, thus enabling her to seamlessly integrate into the new environment. She stated that:

“Basin makakuha pud ko or mahatagan ko og chance to teach sa laing nasod so that way maka sabay ko sa ilaha kay we all know that English is a universal language so by that I believe maka provide pud ko og quality education on my future students.” (IDI-07)

(Maybe I will also have the opportunity to teach in another country, so that way, I can blend in with them because we all know that English is a universal language. By doing that, I believe I can also provide quality education to my future students.)

Recognizing English Proficiency as Fundamental Skill in Global Landscape. The second code of the fourth probed issue. The participants' feedback from both the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions suggests that they are motivated to improve their English proficiency due to its importance as a fundamental skill in the global context. Participants discussed how English proficiency enhances their ability to engage in cross-cultural communication and collaboration, allowing them to interact effectively with individuals from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds.

Learnstar (pseudonym) emphasized that in the learning English is crucial in the context of globalization, where English frequently serves as a common language for communication across diverse regions. Proficiency in English facilitates access to global opportunities, including educational resources, professional networks, and cultural exchanges. In the interview, she mentioned:

“Ang maka influence nga mag dapat maglearn jud diay dapat og English kay naa na biya ta sa globalization nga ano karun no niya need man jud ta mag English.” (IDI-03)

(It is really important to learn English because we are now influenced by globalization, where English is often necessary.)

Moreover, Wordchaser (pseudonym) underscores that learning English is crucial because it serves as the international language, facilitating communication across different cultures and countries. Proficiency in English opens up opportunities for global interaction, access to international resources, and participation in diverse professional and academic fields. She states that:

“Importante kaayo nga makatuon ta og English since, since English language is the international language.” (IDI-02)

(Learning English is crucial because it is the international language.)

Finally, Fluentdream (pseudonym) expressed that acquiring necessary teaching skills, can expand opportunities beyond the Philippines to teach globally or in other countries if given the chance. Proficiency in English and strong teaching abilities enable individuals to adapt to diverse educational settings and connect with students from various backgrounds. She mentioned that:

“Pag ma possess na nimo ang necessary skills nimo sa teaching you can’t only teach here in the Philippines but also you can teach globally or in another country if given an opportunity.” (IDI-07)

(Once you possess the necessary teaching skills, you can not only teach here in the Philippines but also globally or in another country if given the chance.)

Data Integration of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

The present study on the motivational orientation toward learning English among BEED students in a local college utilizes a mixed methods approach, employing the convergent parallel approach. The third research question of the study involves corroborating the findings from the quantitative and qualitative phases. Table 7 outlines the salient quantitative and qualitative findings, presenting focal points in the first column, which contains the aspects or focal points of the study. This is followed by the quantitative and qualitative findings in the second and third columns, the findings from the quantitative phase typically consist of the items in each indicator, while the qualitative findings, which display the identified responses, confirm, or disconfirm the quantitative results. The fourth column indicates the nature of the data integration, and the fifth column contains the axiological implications based on the data described in the preceding columns.

Table 7. Joint Display of the Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

Aspect or Focal Points	Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Findings	Nature of Data Integration	Axiological Implications
Students’ motivational orientation on learning English in terms of extrinsic orientation	Table 2 on the level of motivational orientation on learning English in terms of extrinsic orientation item no. 4 <i>It will allow me to get good scores of English in school</i> with a mean of 4.52 with a description of very high which means that it is always manifested by the elementary education students.	Table 5 on insights shared by students with regards to the motivational orientation on learning English has a code of motivation plays crucial role on English language learning highlighting the essential theme <i>giving importance to the role of motivation on English language proficiency</i>	Merging-Converging	Students who want to get good scores of English in school knows the importance of the role of motivation on English language proficiency
Students’ motivational orientation on learning English in terms of international orientation	Table 2 on the motivational orientation on learning English in terms of international orientation item no. 1 <i>It will allow me to meet more speakers of English</i> with a mean of 4.39 with a description of very high which means that it is always manifested by the elementary education students.	Table 4 the coping mechanisms of BEED students with regards to the challenges in motivational orientation on learning English has a code of exposing oneself to the language use highlighting the essential theme of <i>improving one’s language proficiency through language exposure and setting priorities</i>	Merging-Converging	The students expose themselves to the language use to improve their language proficiency to enable them to meet more speakers of English
	Table 2 on the motivational orientation on learning English in terms of international orientation item no. 5 <i>It will allow me to learn more about the culture and art</i>	Table 5 on insights shared by students with regards to the motivational orientation on learning English has a code of recognizing English proficiency as fundamental skill in	Merging-Converging	Students recognized the role of English proficiency as fundamental skill in global landscape for them to be able to learn more about the culture and art of English-speaking countries.

	<i>of English-speaking countries with a mean of 4.47 with a description of very high which means that it is always manifested by the elementary education students.</i>	global landscape highlighting the essential theme <i>understanding the role of English proficiency in global context</i>		
Students' motivational orientation on learning English in terms of intrinsic orientation	Table 2 on the motivational orientation on learning English in terms of international orientation item no. 3 <i>Mastering English makes me confident</i> with a mean of 4.20 with a description of very high which means that it is always manifested by the elementary education students.	Table 4 the coping mechanisms of BEED students with regards to the challenges in motivational orientation on learning English has a code of doing self-practice and confidence building in English speaking highlighting the essential theme of <i>improving one's language proficiency through language exposure and setting priorities</i>	Merging-Converging	Students improve their language proficiency through exposure and setting priorities making them master the language and makes them confident on using the language.
	Table 2 on the motivational orientation on learning English in terms of intrinsic orientation item no. 5 <i>I enjoy the satisfaction when I find out new things in English</i> with a mean of 4.39 with a description of very high which means that it is always manifested by the elementary education students.	Table 5 on insights shared by students with regards to the motivational orientation on learning English has a code of emphasizing self-fulfillment and growth in English language proficiency highlighting the essential theme of <i>recognizing that proficiency is essential in personal and professional growth</i>	Merging-Converging	Students enjoy the satisfaction when finding out new things in English emphasizing self-fulfillment and growth in English language proficiency

Students' Motivational Orientation on Learning English in terms of Extrinsic Orientation. In the quantitative phase, the specific item on the extrinsic motivation rated as very high is item number 4 I want to improve my English because it will allow me to get good grades at school with a mean of 4.52. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is themed as giving importance to the role of motivation on English language proficiency. From an axiological perspective, student who wants to get good scores of English in school knows the importance of the role of motivation on English language proficiency. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative.

Students' Motivational Orientation on Learning English in terms of International Orientation. In quantitative phase, item number 1 I want to improve my English because it will allow me to meet more speaker of English on the international orientation has a mean of 4.39 with a description of very high. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is themed as improving one's language proficiency through language exposure and setting priorities. From an axiological perspective, the students expose themselves to the language use to improve their language proficiency to enable them to meet more speakers of English.

Moreover, item number 5 I want to improve my English because it will allow me to learn more about the culture and art of English-speaking has a mean of 4.47 with a description of very high. This result is also connected with the qualitative finding, which is themed as acknowledging the role of English proficiency in global context. From an axiological perspective, students connected with the qualitative finding, which is themed as acknowledging the role of English proficiency in global context. From an axiological

perspective, students recognized the role of English proficiency as fundamental skill in global landscape for them to be able to learn more about the culture and art of English-speaking countries. Hence, the qualitative data converges quantitative data in this aspect.

Students' Motivational Orientation on Learning English in terms of Intrinsic Orientation. In quantitative phase, item number 3 on the intrinsic orientation I want to improve my English because mastering English makes me confident has a mean 4.20 with a description of high. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is themed improving one's language proficiency through language exposure and setting priorities. From an axiological perspective, students enhance their language proficiency through exposure to the language and by prioritizing language learning, which enables them to master the language and gain confidence in using it. Moreover, item number 5 on intrinsic orientation I want to improve my English because I enjoy the satisfaction when I find out new things in English with a mean of 4.39 with a description of very high. This result is connected with the qualitative finding, which is themed recognizing that proficiency is essential in personal and professional growth. From an axiological perspective, students enjoy the satisfaction when finding out new things in English emphasizing self-fulfillment and growth in English language proficiency. Hence, the qualitative data converges quantitative data in this aspect.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

First, the level of motivational orientation on learning English among BEED students is very high in terms of extrinsic orientation, international orientation, and intrinsic orientation. Hence, this indicate that the following indicators are always manifested by the selected elementary education students.

Second, the thematic analysis of the qualitative data was conducted based on the responses obtained from in-depth interviews (IDI) and focus group discussions (FGD). The results provided deeper insights into the lived experiences and challenges faced by elementary education students regarding their motivational orientation in learning English. Qualitatively, the elementary education students experienced different challenges that affects their motivation towards learning English. The following terms emerged: Experiencing Difficulty in Language Learning and Language Use, Having Fear of Judgement Resulting to Lack of Self-Confidence, and Struggling with External Pressure.

Third, from the participants responses, other themes are identified which shows the coping mechanism of elementary education students with regards to their motivational orientation on learning English. The following are the themes: Applying Holistic Approaches to Enhance English Proficiency, Overcoming External Pressure through Self-Encouragement, Improving One's Language Proficiency through Language Exposure and Setting Priorities, and Employing Collaborative Learning and Technological Support.

Fourth, based from the participants responses on the in-depth interview and focus group discussion, other terms are identified which shows the insights shared by elementary education students with regards to the motivational orientation on learning English. This are the following themes emerged: Recognizing that Language Proficiency is Essential in Personal and Professional Growth, Giving Importance to the Role of Motivation on English Language Proficiency, Importance of Having a Supportive Environment for Feedback and Self- Expression, and Acknowledging the Role of English Proficiency in Global Context.

Lastly, to gain a deeper understanding of the influence of motivational orientation on learning English, the responses were analyzed thematically to validate the quantitative findings of the study. The results from both phases were integrated according to the planned approach. The quantitative results indicate the status of motivational orientation toward learning English among elementary education students, which aligns with the data obtained from the qualitative phase. Both quantitative and qualitative findings confirm that, despite the challenges faced by elementary education students in learning English, motivation enables them to overcome these obstacles.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were being drawn:

Given that the intrinsic orientation towards learning English among elementary education students has the lowest mean among the three indicators, potentially affecting students' intrinsic desire to learn English, it is advised that students actively work to bolster their intrinsic orientation towards English learning. This can be achieved by employing various strategies such as seeking personal connections within the language, exploring topics and interests that genuinely engage their curiosity and passion, and immersing themselves in activities such as reading books, watching movies, or listening to music in English that resonate with their interests. The institution can also establish English clubs where students can participate in discussions, debates, and other language-related activities. By adopting these approaches, students can effectively enhance their motivation towards learning English.

Moreover, the challenges unearthed through qualitative analysis, including language learning difficulties, fear of judgment, and external pressure, significantly impact students' motivation to learn the language. Therefore, interventions need to be customized to tackle these particular issues. Implementing the coping mechanisms shared by participants regarding their motivational orientation towards learning English can assist students in sustaining their motivation for language acquisition. Moreover, the institution may include activities like public speaking clubs or small-group discussions to help students build confidence and reduce anxiety in using English Language..

Also, new strategies can be used by the students to help them maintain their motivation to learn the English language. Lastly, based on the insights shared by elementary education students regarding motivational orientation towards learning English, it is crucial to

emphasize the importance of language proficiency in both personal and professional growth, highlighting the practical benefits of mastering English. Moreover, it is also important to underscore the pivotal role of motivation in enhancing English language proficiency, encouraging students to cultivate a positive mindset towards learning. Additionally, creating a supportive environment that fosters constructive feedback and encourages self-expression can significantly enhance students' motivation and language skills. Lastly, emphasizing the global relevance of English proficiency can motivate students by highlighting its importance in a connected and diverse world.

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